

Review article

Impact of coffee intake on human aging: Epidemiology and cellular mechanisms

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ABSTRACT

The conception of coffee consumption has undergone a profound modification, evolving from a noxious habit into a safe lifestyle actually preserving human health. The last 20 years also provided strikingly consistent epidemiological evidence showing that the regular consumption of moderate doses of coffee attenuates all-cause mortality, an effect observed in over 50 studies in different geographic regions and different ethnicities. Coffee intake attenuates the major causes of mortality, dampening cardiovascular-, cerebrovascular-, cancer- and respiratory diseases-associated mortality, as well as some of the major causes of functional deterioration in the elderly such as loss of memory, depression and frailty. The amplitude of the benefit seems discrete (17% reduction) but nonetheless corresponds to an average increase in healthspan of 1.8 years of lifetime. This review explores evidence from studies in humans and human tissues supporting an ability of coffee and of its main components (caffeine and chlorogenic acids) to preserve the main biological mechanisms responsible for the aging process, namely genomic instability, macromolecular damage, metabolic and proteostatic impairments with particularly robust effects on the control of stress adaptation and inflammation and unclear effects on stem cells and regeneration. Further studies are required to detail these mechanistic benefits in aged individuals, which may offer new insights into understanding of the biology of aging and the development of new senostatic strategies. Additionally, the safety of this lifestyle factor in the elderly prompts a renewed attention to recommending the maintenance of coffee consumption throughout life as a healthy lifestyle and to further exploring who gets the greater benefit with what schedules of which particular types and doses of coffee.

1. An aging world

The population worldwide is aging at an accelerated pace, with an increasing number of aged individuals in European countries currently reaching 22.9–24.0% of the population in countries such as Portugal or Italy (Lopes et al., 2023; The Lancet Regional Health-Europe, 2023). But, also in other continents, such as Africa that now has the highest birth rate, the demographic projections predict that the number of older Africans will triple in the next 3 decades (He et al., 2020).

Living longer has always been a desire nurtured by humans, but this increased longevity might not be of interest if it is not accompanied by a sustained health status to ensure autonomy and quality of life. Thus, we should aspire to increase healthspan on aging rather than only lifespan

or longevity (Olshansky, 2018). In fact, the current increased life expectancy in Western countries seems to be a longevity trap, whereby people live longer but with several chronic diseases that often severely limit their quality of life (Freeman, 2011; Iburg et al., 2023). It is often overlooked that aging is, by far, the major predictor of the development of most chronic debilitating diseases such as stroke (Michael and Shaughnessy, 2006), cardiovascular diseases (North and Sinclair, 2012), cancer (Montégut et al., 2024), Alzheimer's disease and other dementia (Hou et al., 2019) or chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (Postma et al., 2015) just to name the chronic age-associated diseases with the larger incidence and imposing the largest socio-economic burden (Goldman, 2015; Marengoni et al., 2011). Additionally, there is a gradual deterioration of several physiological processes that limit the

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quality of life, including the progressive emergence of frailty, poorer sleep quality, deterioration of sensory systems, depression and difficulties in decision making. The evolution and amplification of several of these age-related diseases and malfunctions are often the cause of death. Paradoxically, it is very common to expect that elderly people should be afflicted by age-associated diseases, but it is rare to attribute 'extreme age' as a cause of death. This justifies the increased interest in the characteristics of this aging process and in procedures to dampen age-associated chronic diseases with the hope of increasing healthspan on aging and eventually also longevity.

The aging process is best characterized by a progressive functional deterioration associated with a larger variability of physiological parameters (Timiras, 2007) that affects the required homeostasis (dynamic equilibrium between a living organism and its environment, in the absence of modifications of the environment; Cannon, 1929). Homeostasis is possible thanks to different combinations of different physiological parameters and different individuals find different combinations of physiological parameters to reach it (Marder and Taylor, 2011). This justifies the increased variability of physiological and biochemical parameters with aging. Aging is also associated with a deterioration of allostasis (the ability of an organism to shift its homeostasis with alterations of the environment). This allostatic compression associated with aging provides a rationale to understand how aging is the major risk factor for age-associated chronic diseases: aged organisms can only adapt to a narrow range of environmental alterations, being far more prone to fail finding homeostatic solutions in an ever-changing environment, and a lack of homeostasis is the hallmark of a disease state.

The efforts to understand the biology of aging in the last 20 years have unveiled numerous key processes contributing to the aging process. These processes were brilliantly organized in a simplified framework by several researchers gathered around Felipe Sierra, who proposed a scheme of 7 pillars of aging, namely macromolecular damage, epigenetics, metabolism, proteostasis, inflammation, adaptation to stress and stem cells and regeneration (Kennedy et al., 2014). This framework of alterations, continuously revised and updated (López-Otín et al., 2023), includes changes both within and between cells and predicts that any combination of these modifications could precipitate the aging process.

This review will first provide an updated compilation of the epidemiological evidence linking the consumption of coffee with an increased lifespan, pointing out several unsolved questions that still need to be clarified. This will be bridged with a brief survey of the most representative epidemiological studies documenting the effects of coffee intake on the most common diseases causing death on aging. We will then explore the even more important relation between coffee intake and healthspan on aging by providing a summary of the evidence supporting an impact of coffee intake on the major alterations leading to the loss of quality of life in the elderly. Finally, we will attempt the first comprehensive analysis of the possible impact of coffee and of some of its major constituents on the biological mechanisms (the 7 pillars of aging) proposed to underlie the aging process, focusing solely on evidence gathered in humans and human tissues. Overall, it is hoped that this review will bolster the interest in detailing the molecular mechanisms linking the intake of coffee with better quality of the aging process.

2. Impact of coffee intake on longevity

2.1. Coffee constituents and their biological impact

Although it is always risky to consider any particular nutrient isolated from a food matrix, there is accumulating evidence linking the intake of coffee with increased lifespan and healthspan on aging (Grosso et al., 2017a; Kim et al., 2022; Takahashi and Ishigami, 2017). Coffee is the most consumed beverage after water (Martin et al., 2020) with 2.25 billion cups consumed every day by circa 70 % of the world population (<https://www.statista.com/statistics/292595/global-coffee-consumpti>

on/). Coffee is a mixture of over 2000 potentially bioactive substances (de Melo Pereira et al., 2020), with particularly high levels of chlorogenic acids and caffeine (e.g. Angeloni et al., 2020) and with other substances such as melanoidins, diterpenes and trigonelline also potentially able to trigger biological effects that are still poorly characterized (reviewed in Machado et al., 2023; Makiso et al., 2023). Several beneficial effects have been associated to melanoidins, such as antioxidant, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, antihypertensive and prebiotic activity (Moreira et al., 2012; Rufián-Henares and Pastoriza, 2015; Shaheen et al., 2022). Chlorogenic acids are polyphenols present in numerous foods and are assumed to afford health benefits by acting as antioxidants although several other targets have been proposed, such as inhibition of TLR4-mediated activation of NF- κ B to control inflammation, modulation of the signal transduction through the PI3K/AKT/PTEEN pathway to control cellular differentiation, regulation of the AMPK/ACC/CPT-1 signaling pathway to control the immune system and control of lipid and carbohydrate metabolism affording metabolic resilience (Meng et al., 2013; Murai and Matsuda, 2023; Naveed et al., 2018; Nguyen et al., 2024; Tajik et al., 2017; Yun et al., 2022). However, in an average diet, coffee only contributes up to 40 % of the total estimated intake of polyphenols (Burkholder-Coolley et al., 2016; Fukushima et al., 2014; Zamora-Ros et al., 2016), which questions if the effects of coffee mostly result from its content in chlorogenic acids. In contrast, coffee is the main contributor to the intake of caffeine in 'average' Western diets of adults (EFSA, 2015; Mitchell et al., 2015), reaching over 90 % in the elderly (dePaula and Farah, 2019; EFSA, 2015). This leads to the assumption that caffeine might be a main contributor for the effects of coffee intake on human health, although this contention should not dwarf the impact of other coffee constituents some of which have been shown to synergize with caffeine to affect human health (Johnston et al., 2003; Zheng et al., 2014). Caffeine is traditionally assumed to have multiple targets, namely, to inhibit the activity of phosphodiesterases and to control the release of calcium from intracellular stores (e.g. Benowitz, 1990; Magkos and Kavouras, 2005; Rodak et al., 2021). Although acceptable from the strict pharmacological point of view, these targets of caffeine are simply irrelevant from the physiological point of view since the concentrations of caffeine required to affect phosphodiesterases or calcium release are never attained in living organisms (Fredholm et al., 1999). Thus, the only known physiologically relevant mechanism of action of caffeine is the antagonism of adenosine receptors (Fredholm et al., 1999). These adenosine receptors come into two major subtypes, inhibitory A₁ receptors and facilitatory A_{2A} receptors (Fredholm et al., 2005); their endogenous ligand, adenosine (which is required to tonically activate the receptors for caffeine to have an effect) has two roles: decreasing basal responses through A₁ receptor activation and bolstering transition states in adaptive responses by activating A_{2A} receptors (Izerman et al., 2022). Accordingly, the acute effects of caffeine intake result from counteracting adenosine A₁ receptor activation, justifying the increased awareness, attention and reactivity (i.e. increased physical and mental performance or readiness for performance) upon acute coffee intake (Dunwiddie and Masino, 2001). These mainly central effects of caffeine, resulting from the abundance of A₁ receptor far greater in the brain than elsewhere in the body (Fredholm et al., 2005), prompted designating caffeine as the most widely consumed psychostimulant (McLellan et al., 2016). In contrast, the impact of the chronic consumption of coffee is mostly attributed to the control of adenosine A_{2A} receptor-mediated effects, counteracting potentially mis-adaptive responses and preventing transitions to abnormal cellular and tissue dysfunction (Cunha, 2016). In this sense, the regular intake of moderate doses of coffee is expected to afford a functional normalization and stabilize the organism. Since coffee consumers are not episodic but rather regular consumers of caffeine, this should prompt consider designating caffeine as a normalizer rather than as a psychostimulant substance.

2.2. Coffee intake and lifespan

In accordance with this rationale, it may not be surprising that the intake of coffee should preserve health upon aging, which is essentially characterized by an allostatic dysfunction. In fact, epidemiological studies concur in deducing that the regular consumption of moderate doses of coffee is associated with an increased lifespan, a conclusion emerging from both meta-analyses (Crippa et al., 2014; Di Maso et al., 2021; Grosso et al., 2016a; Je and Giovannucci, 2014; Kim et al., 2019; Li et al., 2019; Malerba et al., 2013; Shin et al., 2022; Zhao et al., 2015) and narrative reviews (Bhatti et al., 2013; O'Keefe et al., 2013; Takahashi and Ishigami, 2017). This association was noted in over 50 different cohort analyzed in different geographical locations, namely in Europe (e.g. Grosso et al., 2017; Gunter et al., 2017; Happonen et al., 2008; Kleemola et al., 2000; Lof et al., 2015; Loftfield et al., 2018; Navarro et al., 2018; Ruggiero et al., 2021; see Table 1) in Americas (e.g. Ding et al., 2015; Freedman et al., 2012; Gardener et al., 2013; Loftfield et al., 2015; Lopez-Garcia et al., 2008; Park et al., 2017; see Table 2) and in Asia (e.g. Abe et al., 2019; Kim et al., 2021; Odegaard et al., 2015; Sado et al., 2019; Saito et al., 2015; Tamakoshi et al., 2011; see Table 3). Notably, stronger associations are found in Europe and in Asia than in the US (Je and Giovannucci, 2014), which highlights the importance of both different food matrixes as well as different lifestyles when analyzing the impact on human health of any individual food component. Some possible confounding effects have been carefully investigated in several studies, particularly the effect of smoking, a habit related to coffee intake (Klesges et al., 1994; Treloar et al., 2014; Treur et al., 2016) and with a robust negative impact on life expectancy (e.g. Christensen et al., 2018; Thun et al., 2013). The stratification of the studied populations by smoking status contributed to reduce heterogeneity, with a more evident decreased risk of coffee intake on all-cause of death in non-smokers and a weak association between coffee intake and mortality when considering smokers (Grosso et al., 2016a). As for smoking, the protective effect of coffee consumption was also stronger when stratification by alcohol intake was performed (Grosso et al., 2017; Gunter et al., 2017). However, other confounding factors such as adding sugar, flavored syrup or cream to coffee should also be studied since they are also expected to offset the benefits on lifespan afforded by the consumption of basic black coffee (Liu et al., 2022; Treskes et al., 2023; Zhang et al., 2021).

The meta-analyses globally identified non-linear inverse associations between coffee intake and mortality with the lowest relative risk (RR) corresponding to an intake of circa 3 cups/day, irrespective of different confounding factors (Grosso et al., 2016a; Kim et al., 2019; Poole et al., 2017). Importantly, all the epidemiological studies were essentially cohort and observational studies where the intake of coffee/caffeine was based on self-applied questionnaires rather than using objective biomarkers. Furthermore, several of the studies relied on questionnaires applied only at baseline and ignored the possibility of alterations in the intake of coffee/caffeine during the follow up period. This leaves some room for the refinement of the collected information, although it does not seem evident to expect the emergence of randomized controlled trials in elderly populations in view of the wild availability of coffee/-caffeine, the prevalence of its intake by most of the population and the potential confounding effects of coffee/caffeine withdrawal (Juliano and Griffiths, 2004).

2.3. Who benefits from the impact of coffee on lifespan?

The risk ratio linking coffee consumption and all-cause mortality is computed between 0.78 and 0.94 (1 means no association and values below 1 mean an increasingly stronger inverse association). These values of risk ratio correspond to an estimated 15% lower likelihood of dying during the analyzed periods or to a gain of 1.84 years of life expectancy attributed to coffee intake using the Chiang's life table method or 4.7–9.1% of estimated years of life (Di Maso et al., 2021; Doepker

et al., 2022; Grosso et al., 2016a). It is important to keep in mind that odds ratios are average values applicable to the whole population studied, where some more individuals benefit by drinking coffee whereas others may suffer detrimental effects upon coffee consumption, in accordance with interindividual differences in caffeine consumption (Nehlig, 2018). In contrast to most 'anti-aging' interventions that display a gender bias (Bartke et al., 2024; Ng and Hazrati, 2022), the increased lifespan attributed to coffee consumption is observed both in men and in women (e.g. Abe et al., 2019; Freedman et al., 2012; Je and Giovannucci, 2014; Lopez-Garcia et al., 2008; Tamakoshi et al., 2011; Zhao et al., 2015; but see Bhandari et al., 2024; Neves et al., 2018) and in Caucasian individuals as well as in different ethnicities (Gardener et al., 2013; Park et al., 2017). Moreover, the beneficial effect of coffee intake on mortality is present in the general population as well as in individuals afflicted with different diseases such as metabolic syndrome (Wu et al., 2023a), type 2 diabetes (Ding et al., 2024; Komorita et al., 2020; Ma et al., 2023; Neves et al., 2018; Shahinfar et al., 2021), cancer (Gregg et al., 2019; Hu et al., 2018; Mackintosh et al., 2020; Oyeleru et al., 2024; but see Nagle et al., 2024), Parkinson's disease (Paul et al., 2019), hypertension (Chen et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2024a; but see Teramoto et al., 2023), co-infection with human immunodeficiency virus and hepatitis C virus (Carrieri et al., 2017) or who suffered from myocardial infarction (Brown et al., 2016; Miranda et al., 2020; van Dongen et al., 2017) or liver transplantation (Wiltberger et al., 2019).

The inter-individual differences in the biological responses to coffee and caffeine are increasingly recognized to be associated with inter-individual genetic differences or polymorphisms, which constitute the basis on an emergent and fascinating field of 'coffee and caffeine genetics' (reviewed in Cornelis, 2019; Low et al., 2024). The pioneering studies identified polymorphisms of caffeine metabolism, namely in cytochrome P450 (CYP1A1–2) and of the aryl hydrocarbon receptor (AhR, involved in detoxification of xenobiotics), as contributors for different biological effects produced by a different intake of coffee or of caffeine (Amin et al., 2012; Cornelis et al., 2011; Josse et al., 2012; Sulem et al., 2011). The superlative work promoted by Marylin Cornelis has extended the list of caffeine metabolizing genes (ABCG2, a drug efflux membrane transporter, and POR, an oxidoreductase linked to cytochrome P450 function) and unveiled the additional contribution of other genes putatively involved in caffeine actions (BDNF, a growth factor, SLC6A4, a serotonin transporter, and ADORA2A, encoding the adenosine A_{2A} receptor) as well as other genes with still unclear relation to the effects of coffee and caffeine (GCKR and MLXIPL both linked to primary metabolism, HECTD4 integrated in the ubiquitin pathway, PDSS2 controlling ferroptosis and aldehyde dehydrogenase 2 in the Japanese population) (Coffee and Caffeine Genetics Consortium, 2015; reviewed in Low et al., 2024). This genetic variability has an effect size difference of 3–32% in number of cups of caffeinated drink per day per effect allele, which, although remarkable in itself, should warn great care in widely extrapolating this relation to carry out Mendelian randomization studies without proper controls and care in the fallibility of the underlying basis of the methodology, as very wisely pointed out some years ago to make sense of the mix published results (Cornelis, 2019).

In the general population, it is still not fully resolved if the benefits of coffee consumption on lifespan result from a long-term benefit associated with the consumption of coffee during adulthood and/or if the consumption of coffee by the elderly provides an on-going protective effect. In fact, for practical temporal reasons, most epidemiological studies in the general population focused on a population aged 50 years or more, which at least enables to conclude that coffee consumption has a consistent benefit on lifespan in individuals aged 50 or more. The few studies that enrolled individuals with a sufficient age interval to allow capturing different benefits of coffee consumption at different ages, actually reached different conclusions, some arguing for stronger associations between coffee and mortality in individuals aged more than 55 years (Lof et al., 2015; Navarro et al., 2018) and others concluding a

Table 1
Epidemiological studies on the association of coffee consumption with mortality in Europe.

reference	country	participants & follow-up	type of coffee and evaluation	odds ratio	dose-dependence
Jacobsen et al. (1986)	Norway	11,5 years follow-up of 13,664 men and 2891 women aged 38–72 years	any coffee single questionnaire	OR death of 0.84 (0.73–0.94)	-
Vandenbroucke et al. (1986)	Netherlands	25 years follow-up of 1583 men and 1508 women aged 40–65 years	any coffee repeated questionnaire	OR death of 1.65 (1.11–2.44) for men and 0.86 (0.54–1.35) for women drinking ≥ 5 cups/day	no
Rosengren and Wilhelmsen (1991)	Sweden	7.1-years follow-up of 6765 men aged 51–59 years	filtered coffee questionnaire at baseline	OR death of 0.6 (0.3–0.9) for ≥ 9 cups/day	-
Hart and Smith (1997)	Scotland	21 years follow up of 5766 men aged 35–64 years	any coffee questionnaire in 1970 & 1977	OR death of 0.97 (0.69–1.36) for 2–4 cups/day	no
Woodward and Tunstall-Pedoe (1999)	Scotland	7.7-years follow-up of over 11,000 men and women, aged 40–59 years	any coffee questionnaire at baseline	OR death of 0.74 for men and 0.77 for women drinking 3–4 cups/day	U shape, trend; nadir at 3–4 cups/day
Kleemola et al. (2000)	Finland	10 years follow up of 20,179 men and women aged 30–59 years	any coffee questionnaire at baseline	OR death of 0.97 (0.82–1.14) for men and 0.79 (0.63–1.01) for women drinking 4–7 cups/day	-
Jazbec et al. (2003)	Croatia	30 years follow up of 1571 men and 1793 women aged 35–59 years	any coffee questionnaire in 1972 & 1982	OR death of 0.77 (0.61–0.98) for men and 0.63 (0.46–0.86) for women drinking 1–2 cups/day	-
Happonen et al. (2008)	Finland	14.5 years follow-up of 6960 person-years aged 70–94 years	any coffee questionnaire at baseline & 2–3 years after	OR death of 0.90 (0.70–1.15) for 5–6 cups/day	Linear up to 7 cups/day
Lof et al. (2015)	Sweden	10 years follow-up of 45,140 Swedish women aged 30–49 years	any coffee questionnaire at baseline	OR death 0.81 (0.69–0.94) for 2–5 cups/day	-
Gunter et al. (2017)	10 Europe cohorts	16.4 years follow-up of 521,330 men and women aged >35 years	any coffee questionnaire at baseline & final	OR death 0.88 (0.82–0.95) for men and 0.93 (0.87–0.98) for women drinking >850 mL coffee/day	-
Grosso et al. (2017b)	Czech Republic, Russia, Poland	6.1 years follow up of 28,561 men and women aged 35–59 years	any coffee questionnaire at baseline	OR death of 0.83 (0.71–0.99) for men and 0.63 (0.47–0.84) for women drinking 3–4 cups/day	-
van Dongen et al. (2017)	Netherlands	10 years follow up of 4362 men and women with previous myocardial infarction aged 60–80 years	any coffee questionnaire at baseline	OR death of 0.82 (0.68–0.98) for ≥ 4 cups/day	-
Carrieri et al. (2017)	France	5 years follow up of 1028 men and women with HIV-HCV co-infection aged > 18 years	any coffee annual questionnaire	OR death of 0.5 (0.3–0.9) for ≥ 3 cups/day	-
van den Brandt (2018)	Netherlands	10 years follow-up of 58,279 men and 62,573 women aged 55–69 years	any coffee questionnaire at baseline	OR death of 1.22 (0.89–1.66) for men and 0.65 (0.47–0.90) for women drinking ≥ 6 cups/day	-
Loftfield et al. (2018)	United Kingdom	10 years follow-up of 498,134 men and women aged 38–73 years	decaffeinated, instant, ground coffee questionnaire in 2006 & 2010	OR death of 0.90 (0.85–0.95) for 2–3 cups/day OR death of 0.80 (0.74–0.87) for 2–3 cups/day OR death of 0.85 (0.78–0.93) for 2–3 cups/day	Linear trend up to 7 cups/day
Navarro et al. (2018)	Spain	10 years follow-up of 19,888 men and women aged 38±10 years	caffeinated, decaffeinated coffee questionnaire at baseline	OR death of 0.77 (0.64–0.92) for each 2 cups/day OR death of 0.83 (0.62–1.12) for each 2 cups/day	Linear trend up to 4 cups/day
Torres-Collado et al. (2019)	Spain	12 years follow-up of 903 men and women aged > 65 years	caffeinated, decaffeinated coffee questionnaire at baseline	OR death of 0.73 (0.50–1.06) for >1 cup/day OR death of 0.82 (0.57–1.19) for >1 cup/day	-
Wiltberger et al. (2019)	Germany	1 year follow-up of 90 men and women with liver transplantation due to hepatocellular carcinoma aged 48–73 years	any coffee questionnaire before/after surgery	OR death of 0.29 (0.12–0.71) for ≥ 1 cup/day	-
Petimar et al. (2019)	5 Europe, US, Australia cohorts	12–24 years follow-up of 351,565 men and women at risk of amyotrophic lateral sclerosis aged 27–89 years	caffeinated coffee caffeine questionnaire at baseline	OR death of 1.04 (0.74–1.47) for ≥ 3 cups/day OR death of 0.99 (0.80–1.23) for 500 mg/day	-
Lukic et al. (2020)	Norway	20.5 years follow-up of 117,228 women aged 30–70 years	filtered coffee instant coffee boiled coffee questionnaire at baseline	OR death of 0.89 (0.83–0.94) for 4–6 cups/day OR death of 0.90 (0.85–0.96) for 4–6 cups/day OR death of 0.96 (0.99–1.05) for 4–6 cups/day	J shape; nadir at 4 cups/day (linear in never-smokers)
Tverdal et al. (2020)	Norway	20 years follow-up of 508,747 men and women aged 20–79 years	unfiltered coffee filtered coffee	OR death of 0.96 (0.91–1.01) for 1–8 cups/day men OR death of 0.91 (0.86–0.96) for 1–8	Linear, flattens at 4 cups/day

(continued on next page)

Table 1 (continued)

reference	country	participants & follow-up	type of coffee and evaluation	odds ratio	dose-dependence
			questionnaire at baseline	cups/day women OR death of 0.85 (0.82–0.90) for 1–8 cups/day men OR death of 0.85 (0.81–0.90) for 1–8 cups/day women	
Torres-Collado et al. (2021)	Spain	18 years follow-up of 1567 men and women aged > 20 years	caffeinated, decaffeinated coffee questionnaire at baseline	OR death of 0.59 (0.44–0.79) for 1–6 cups/day OR death of 0.76 (0.56–1.03) for 1–6 cups/day	-
Ruggiero et al. (2021)	Italy	8.3 years follow-up of 20,487 men and women aged 35–94 years	any coffee questionnaire at baseline	OR death of 0.72 (0.57–0.92) for 3–4 cups/day	J-shaped; nadir at 3–4 cups/day
Chieng et al. (2022)	United Kingdom	12.5 years follow-up of 449,563 men and women aged 38–73 years	decaffeinated ground coffee instant coffee questionnaire at baseline	OR death of 0.86 (0.81–0.91) for 2–3 cups/day OR death of 0.73 (0.69–0.78) for 2–3 cups/day OR death of 0.89 (0.86–0.93) for 2–3 cups/day	2–3 cups/day
Simon et al. (2022)	United Kingdom	11 years follow-up of 468,629 men and women aged 40–69 years	any coffee questionnaire at baseline	OR death of 0.88 (0.83–0.92) for 1–3 cups/day	-
Chen et al. (2022a)	United Kingdom	12.1 years follow-up of 498,1158 men and women aged 37–73 years	any coffee questionnaire at baseline	OR death of 0.78 (0.73–0.85) for 1–2 cups/day	J-shaped; nadir at 1–2 cups/day
Liu et al. (2022)	United Kingdom	7 years follow-up of 171,616 men and women aged >35 years	any coffee questionnaire at baseline	OR death of 0.71 (0.62–0.82) for 2–3 cups/day	U-shaped; nadir at 3 cups/day
Schaefer et al. (2023)	United Kingdom	15 years follow-up of 354,386 men and women aged 38–73 years	any coffee questionnaire at baseline	OR death of 1.06 (1.03–1.09) for 2 cups/day	-
Susy (2023)	United Kingdom	12.5 years follow-up of 449,563 men and women aged 40–69 years	ground coffee instant coffee decaffeinated questionnaire at baseline	OR death of 0.73 (0.69–0.78) for 2–3 cups/day OR death of 0.89 (0.86–0.93) for 2–3 cups/day OR death of 0.86 (0.80–0.91) for 2–3 cups/day	U-shaped; nadir at 2–3 cups/day
Mérida et al. (2023)	Spain	12.5 years follow-up of 12,161 men and women aged >18 years	any coffee questionnaire at baseline	OR death of 0.89 (0.80–0.99) for methoxyphenols OR death of 0.59 (0.39–0.90) for alkylmethoxyphenols OR death of 0.63 (0.42–0.94) for hydroxycinnamic acids	-
Wu et al. (2023a)	United Kingdom	13.9 years follow-up of 118,872 patients with metabolic syndrome aged 37–73 years	any coffee questionnaire at baseline	OR death of 0.89 (0.80–0.99) for 2 cups/day	U-shaped; nadir at 2 cups/day
Oyelere et al. (2024)	Netherlands	6.6 years follow-up of 257 patients with colorectal cancer aged 47–61 years	any coffee questionnaire at baseline	OR death of 0.68 (0.53–0.88) for 4 cups/day	U-shaped; nadir at 4 cups/d
Zhang et al. (2024a)	United Kingdom	9 years follow-up of 204,847 participants (44.7 % males) aged 40–69 years (neurodegenerative-related deaths)	caffeinated coffee questionnaire at baseline	OR death of 0.67 (0.44–1.01) for ≥3 cups/day	-

more evident association in younger (<55 years old) individuals (Liu et al., 2013). Interestingly, it was also observed that the consumption of coffee by elderly women (65–81 years) was not significantly associated with survival to age 90 years after adjusting for confounders (Shadyab et al., 2020). These findings may either be due to an attenuation of the association of coffee with mortality during aging of the individuals (Happonen et al., 2008; Torres-Collado et al., 2019) or to the shift of coffee consumption in elderly individuals, who tend to decrease their intake of caffeinated coffee and increase that of decaffeinated coffee (Grosso et al., 2016b; Torres-Collado et al., 2018). This shift is probably promoted by the traditional clinical recommendations to decrease or even quit coffee consumption at older ages (e.g. Sotos-Prieto et al., 2010), a guideline that ought to be re-evaluated upon analysis of the evidence presented in this review.

2.4. Dose-dependence effects of coffee on lifespan

An observation that often contributes to consolidate the association of a given factor with human health status in epidemiological studies, is

the existence of a dose relation between the evaluated factor and the alteration of human health status. Accordingly, several epidemiological studies and meta-analyses concluded that the benefits of coffee consumption on lifespan follow a J-shaped curve, with discrete benefits afforded by the consumption of 1 cup of coffee a day, maximal benefits afforded by 3 cups a day, followed by a waning of the benefits with increasing doses of coffee consumed daily (Chieng et al., 2022; Crippa et al., 2014; Ding et al., 2015; Freedman et al., 2012; Grosso et al., 2016a; Happonen et al., 2008; Je and Giovannucci, 2014; Kim et al., 2019; Kleemola et al., 2000; Loftfield et al., 2015, 2018; Ruggiero et al., 2021; Saito et al., 2015; Zhao et al., 2015). The decreased benefits on lifespan of higher coffee intake are expected based on the well described negative impact of high doses of coffee intake on behavior of adults, typified by symptoms such as heightened anxiety, agitation restlessness, headaches, insomnia and gastric distress (Temple et al., 2017). These symptoms may lead to a caffeinism syndrome (Iancu et al., 2007), which incidence has not been reported in aged individuals. But outside this range of abnormal and excessive coffee consumption that the majority of people are able to avoid, it should once more be emphasized that the

Table 2
Epidemiological studies on the association of coffee consumption with mortality in Americas.

reference	country	participants & follow-up	type of coffee	odds ratio	dose-dependence
Kahn et al. (1984)	US - California	21 years follow-up of 600 men and women aged >30 years	any coffee questionnaire at baseline	OR death of 1.26 (1.05–1.51)	-
LeGrady et al. (1987)	US - Michigan	19 years follow-up of 1910 men aged 40–55 years	any coffee single questionnaire	OR death of 0.75 for 2–3 cups/day	-
Lindsted et al. (1992)	US - California	26 years follow-up of 9484 men aged 51–59 years	any coffee questionnaire at baseline	OR death of 1.28 (1.12–1.47) for ≥ 3 cups/day	-
Klatsky et al. (1993)	US - California	8 years follow up of 128,934 men and women with a mean age of 46 years	any coffee questionnaire at baseline	OR death of 0.99 (0.97–1.01) for each additional cup/day	-
Andersen et al. (2006)	US - Iowa	15 years follow-up of over 41,836 post-menopausal women, aged 55–69 years	any coffee questionnaire at baseline	OR death of 0.80 (0.72–0.91) for 4–5 cups/day	U-shaped; nadir at 4–5 cups/day
Paganini-Hill et al. (2007)	US - California	23-years follow-up of 8644 women and 4980 men with a mean age of 74 years	caffeine questionnaire at baseline	OR death of 0.90 (0.85–0.94) for 200–400 mg/day	U-shaped; nadir at 200–400 mg /day
Lopez-Garcia et al. (2008)	US	18–24 years follow up of 41,736 men and 86,214 women aged 30–59 years	all coffee decaffeinated coffee repeated questionnaires	OR death of 0.95 (0.89–1.03) for 2–3 cups/day for men OR death of 0.77 (0.73–0.82) for 2–3 cups/day for women OR death of 0.91 (0.82–1.01) for 2–3 cups/day for men OR death of 0.85 (0.77–0.94) for 2–3 cups/day for women	linear for men; U-shaped for women, nadir at 3–4 cups/day
Freedman et al. (2012)	US	14 years follow up of 229,119 men and 173,141 women aged 50–71 years	all coffee decaffeinated coffee questionnaire at baseline	OR death of 0.88 (0.84–0.93) for 4–5 cups/day for men OR death of 0.84 (0.79–0.90) for 4–5 cups/day for women OR death of 0.81 (0.69–0.88) for men OR death of 0.78 (0.66–0.87) for women	U-shaped for men and women, nadir at 4–5 cups/day
Liu et al. (2013)	US	17 years follow-up of 43,727 men and women aged 20–87 years	any coffee questionnaire at baseline	OR death of 1.21 (1.04–1.40) for >4 cups/day for men OR death of 1.21 (0.78–1.88) for >4 cups/day for women	-
Lehrer et al. (2013)	US – New York	20 years follow-up of 96 women with breast cancer aged 40–75 years	any coffee questionnaire at baseline	Increased cumulative survival for 1–2 cups/day	-
Gardener et al. (2013)	US – New York	11 years follow-up of 2461 multi-ethnic men and women aged > 40 years	caffeinated coffee decaffeinated questionnaire at baseline	OR death of 0.93 (0.88–0.99) for each additional cup OR death of 0.88 (0.79–0.98) for each additional cup	Linear trend up to 4 cups/day
Ding et al. (2015)	US	16.4 years follow-up of 40,557 men and 167,944 women aged 25–75 years	caffeinated coffee decaffeinated repeated questionnaires	OR death of 0.93 (0.90–0.96) for 1–3 cups/day OR death of 0.94 (0.88–1.00) for 1–3 cups/day	U-shaped, nadir at 2 cups/day
Lofffield et al. (2015)	US	13 years follow up of 90,317 men and women aged 55–74 years	caffeinated coffee decaffeinated single questionnaire	OR death of 0.82 (0.77–0.88) for 2–3 cups/day OR death of 0.88 (0.75–1.04) for 2–3 cups/day	-
Loomba et al. (2016)	US	7 years follow-up of 8608 men and women aged > 45 years	any coffee questionnaire at baseline	OR death of 0.80 (0.70–0.91) for 2–3 cups/day; after adjustments becomes 0.86 (0.56–1.34)	-
Park et al. (2017)	US – Hawaii & California	16.2 years follow-up of 185,855 multi-ethnic men and women aged 45–65 years	caffeinated coffee decaffeinated questionnaire at baseline	OR death of 0.79 (0.76–0.83) for 2–3 cups/day OR death of 0.85 (0.75–0.95) for 2–3 cups/day	-
Tsujimoto et al. (2017)	US	6.5 years follow-up of 17,594 men and women aged 20–79 years	Caffeine questionnaire at baseline	OR death of 0.63 (0.51–0.78) for 100–200 mg/day	-
Hu et al. (2018)	US	7.8 years follow-up of 1599 women with colorectal cancer aged 40–75 years	caffeinated coffee decaffeinated repeated questionnaires	OR death of 0.75 (0.62–0.91) for ≥ 2 cups/day OR death of 0.70 (0.55–0.87) for ≥ 2 cups/day	-
Neves et al. (2018)	US	57 months follow-up of 1974 women and 1974 men with diabetes aged 57–62 years	caffeine questionnaire at baseline	OR death of 0.39 (0.23–0.64) for ≥ 200 mg of caffeine/day	Linear trend
Gregg et al. (2019)	US - Texas	3 years follow-up of 411 men with lower prostate cancer aged 65 \pm 9 years	any coffee questionnaire at baseline	OR death of 0.64 (0.29–1.43) for 1–2 cups/day	U-like shape; nadir at 1–4 cups/day

(continued on next page)

Table 2 (continued)

reference	country	participants & follow-up	type of coffee	odds ratio	dose-dependence
Paul et al. (2019)	US - California	5.3 years follow-up of 244 men and women with Parkinson's disease aged 67±10 years	caffeinated coffee single questionnaire	OR death of 0.47 (0.32–0.69) for consumers	-
Shadyab et al. (2020)	US	25 years follow-up of 27,480 multi-ethnic women aged 65–81 years	caffeinated coffee decaffeinated questionnaire at baseline	OR reaching 90 years of age: 1.03 (0.95–1.11) for 2–3 cups/day OR reaching 90 years of age: 1.06 (0.97–1.16) for 2–3 cups/day	-
Mackintosh et al. (2020)	US - Southwest	5.4 years follow-up of 1171 patients with colorectal cancer aged 51–67 years	any coffee questionnaire at baseline	OR death of 0.64 (0.46–0.87) for ≥ 4 cups/day	-
Miranda et al. (2020)	Brazil	4.1 years follow-up of 928 patients with acute coronary syndrome aged > 18 years	any coffee single questionnaire	OR death of 0.13 (0.06–0.29) for 1–2 cups/day	-
Zhang et al. (2021)	US	7.9 years follow-up of 31,402 men and women aged > 20 years	unsweetened coffee single questionnaire	OR death of 0.93 (0.89–0.98) for 1 cup/day	-
Feng et al. (2021)	US	10 years follow-up of 23,878 men and women aged 20–85 years	Caffeine single questionnaire	OR death of 0.68 (0.60–0.78) for >200 mg/day	-
Zheng et al. (2022)	US	9.5 years follow-up of 626 cardiovascular patients aged > 18 years	caffeinated coffee caffeine decaffeinated questionnaire at baseline	OR death of 1.26 (1.26–1–26) for 1–3 cups/day OR death of 0.98 (0.98–0.98) OR death of 0.91 (0.91–0.91) for 1–3 cups/day	-
Lin et al. (2022)	US	8.3 years follow-up of 37,211 men and women aged 35–94 years	Caffeine single questionnaire	OR death of 0.61 (0.42–0.89) for 100–200 mg/day	-
Chen et al. (2022b)	US	6.86 years follow-up of 6076 hypertensive patients aged > 65 years	Caffeine single questionnaire	OR death of 0.70 (0.56–0.87) for 200–300 mg/day	U-like shape; nadir at 200–300 mg/day
Ma et al. (2023a)	US	18.5 years follow-up of 15,486 type 2 diabetes patients aged 30–75 years	any coffee repeated questionnaires	OR death of 0.74 (0.63–0.86) for 4 cups/day	-
Lin et al. (2023)	US	6.5 years follow-up of 2584 individuals with cognitive impairment aged > 60 years	caffeinated coffee caffeine decaffeinated repeated questionnaires	OR death of 0.50 (0.29–0.84) for ≤ 3 cups/day OR death of 0.59 (0.43–0.81) for ≤ 250 mg /day OR death of 0.47 (0.27–0.82) for ≤ 3 cups /day	U-shape; nadir at 1–2 cups/day
Castañeda et al. (2024)	Mexico	11.2 years follow-up of 95,313 women aged >35 years	hydroxycinnamic acids questionnaire at baseline	OR death of 0.79 (0.69–0.81) for 3–5 cups/day	-
Zhou et al. (2024)	US	6.5 years follow-up of 10,639 men and women with average age of 47 ±0.3 years	any coffee single questionnaire	OR death of 0.67 (0.54–0.84) for 1–3 cups/day	-
Nagle et al. (2024)	10 cohorts from Europe, US, Australia	5.3–22.3 years follow-up of 5724 women with ovarian cancer aged 57 years	caffeinated coffee decaffeinated coffee single questionnaire	OR death of 0.94 (0.84–1.05) for 1–2.5 cups/day OR death of 0.97 (0.85–1.10)	-
Vilar-Gomez et al. (2024)	US	23.2 years follow-up of 4361 adults aged ≥20 years (liver-related specific mortality)	any coffee single questionnaire	adjusted sub-hazard ratio death of 0.05 (0.06–0.10) for ≥3 cups/day	-
Wang et al. (2024a)	US	20 years follow-up of 12,093 hypertensive patients aged 57–61 years	Caffeine double questionnaire	OR death of 0.71 (0.60–0.84) for >300 to ≤400 mg/day	U-shape trend, nadir at 300–400 mg

concluded optimal dose of 2–3 cups a day is an average that does not take into consideration the inter-individual variability to the effects of coffee (Fulton et al., 2018; Kapellou et al., 2023; Nehlig, 2018), as well as different factors influencing this recommendation, such as coffee type, preparation methods, and caffeine content. Notably, this optimal dose of 2–3 coffees/day determined for adults coincides with the amount of coffee associated with maximal attenuation of death upon aging. However, there is currently no hard data to guide on the optimal dose of coffee for the elderly, which is expected to be altered in view of the alterations upon aging of the absorption, elimination and sensitivity to coffee components. In fact, there is an alteration of both the pharmacokinetics (pattern of absorption, distribution and elimination in the body) and of the pharmacodynamics (one's sensitivity) of coffee components: whereas the bioavailability of caffeine is similar in young and elderly men (Blanchard and Sawers, 1983), its metabolic clearance may be reduced by 33% in volunteers with 65–85 years (Polasek et al., 2013). There are also coffee-related pharmacodynamic alterations upon aging, such as increased redox features (Liguori et al., 2018) that are targeted by chlorogenic acids, as well as the targets of caffeine - adenosine A_{2A} receptors (Lovász et al., 2022; Temido-Ferreira et al., 2020)

and A₁ receptors (Meyer et al., 2007; Mishina et al., 2017). This prompts the need to carefully evaluate the optimal recommended dose of coffee and of caffeine for the elderly, as well as the safety margin for coffee-/caffeine intake in the elderly. Although the benefits associated with coffee intake on aging argue for a general safety profile in the elderly, the change of the metabolism and sensitivity to coffee and caffeine prompts a need of careful future studies to confirm the safety margin of coffee intake in the elderly.

2.5. Which coffee components affect lifespan?

A final question related to the impact on lifespan of coffee consumption is linked to attempting to gauge if the benefit is mostly ascribed to caffeine or other predominant components in coffee such as chlorogenic acids or melanoidins. The benefits on lifespan were noted for the consumption of different types of coffee, namely ground coffee, instant, boiled coffee or espresso (Chieng et al., 2022; Freedman et al., 2012; Loftfield et al., 2018; Lukic et al., 2020; Susy, 2023). However, the size effect of different types of coffee is similar in some studies (Loftfield et al., 2018; Lukic et al., 2020) but apparently different in other studies,

Table 3
Epidemiological studies on the association of coffee consumption with mortality in Asia.

reference	country	participants & follow-up	type of coffee and evaluation	odds ratio	dose-dependence
Wakai et al. (1993)	Japan	2.5 years follow-up of 293 men and women with urinary tract cancer aged 20–89 years	any coffee questionnaire at baseline	OR death of 0.88 (0.49–1.59) for consumers	-
Iwai et al. (2002)	Japan	9.91 years follow-up of 1404 men and 1451 women aged 40–79 years	any coffee questionnaire at baseline	OR death of 0.43 (0.30–0.63) for >2 cups/day for men OR death of 0.76 (0.45–1.27) for >2 cups/day for women	-
Sugiyama et al. (2010)	Japan	10.3 years follow-up of 18,287 men and 19,455 women aged 40–64 years	any coffee questionnaire at baseline	OR death of 0.82 (0.66–1.02) for 1–2 cups/day in women OR death of 0.91 (0.78–1.06) for 1–2 cups/day in men	Linear up to 4 cups/day
Mineharu et al. (2011)	Japan	12 years follow-up of 76,979 men and women aged 40–79 years	any coffee questionnaire at baseline	OR death of 0.45 (0.17–0.87) for ≥ 3 cups/day	-
Tamakoshi et al. (2011)	Japan	16 years follow-up of 97,753 men and women aged 40–69 years	any coffee questionnaire at baseline	OR death of 0.86 (0.81–0.93) for 1–2 cups/day	U-like shape; nadir at 1–2 cups/day
Saito et al. (2015)	Japan	18.7 years follow-up of 5082 men and 4050 women never smokers aged 40–69 years	any coffee single questionnaire	OR death of 0.76 (0.70–0.83) for 3–4 cups/day for men OR death of 0.80 (0.67–0.97) for 3–4 cups/day for women	U-like shape; nadir at 3–4 cups/day
Odegaard et al. (2015)	Singapore	46 years follow up of 36,925 never smokers men and women aged 45–74 years	any coffee single questionnaire	OR death of 0.83 (0.77–0.90) for >2 cups/day	-
Yamakawa et al. (2019)	Japan	14.1 years follow-up of 410,352 men and 86,214 women aged >35 years	any coffee questionnaire at baseline	OR death of 0.81 (0.71–0.92) for 2–3 cups/day	-
Abe et al. (2019)	Japan	17.3 years follow up of 144,750 men and 168,631 women aged 40–103 years	any coffee questionnaire at baseline	OR death of 0.87 (0.83–0.91) for 1–4 cups/day for men OR death of 0.87 (0.80–0.95) for 1–4 cups/day for women	-
Sado et al. (2019)	Japan	15 years follow up of 39,685 men and 43,124 women aged 40–79 years	any coffee single questionnaire	OR death of 0.71 (0.65–0.78) for 3–4 cups/day	Linear up to 5 cups/day
Komorita et al. (2020)	Japan	5.3 years follow up of 4923 diabetic men and women with mean age of 66 years	any coffee questionnaire at baseline	OR death of 0.59 (0.42–0.82) for ≥ 2 cups/day	-
Teramoto et al. (2021)	Japan	18.5 years follow-up of 46,213 subjects (478 stroke survivors) aged 40–79 years	any coffee repeated questionnaire	OR death of 0.82 (0.77–0.89) for ≥ 2 cups/day	-
Kim et al. (2021)	South Korea	9.1 years follow-up of 173,209 men and women aged >40 years	any coffee questionnaire at baseline	OR death of 0.79 (0.66–0.95) for >3 cups/day	-
Sakamaki et al. (2021)	Japan	18 years follow-up of 9946 men and women aged 19–93 years	any coffee questionnaire at baseline	OR death of 0.82 (0.64–1.07) for 3–4 cups/day	-
Cho et al. (2022)	South Korea	7.7 years follow up of 192,222 men and women aged > 40 years	any coffee questionnaire at baseline	OR death of 0.83 (0.78–0.89) for 1–3 cups/day	U-shape; nadir at 1–2 cups/day
Teramoto et al. (2023)	Japan	18.9 years follow-up of 6574 men and 12,035 women aged 40–79 years	any coffee single questionnaire	OR death of 0.78 (0.48–1.28) for 1 cups/day	-
Mak et al. (2024)	Hong Kong	20 years follow-up of 7420 participants (72.2 % women) average age 53.2 years	any coffee single questionnaire	OR death of 0.82 (0.73–0.93) for >1 cups/day	-

as heralded by the larger effect of ground *versus* instant coffee (Chieng et al., 2022; Susy, 2023) and the larger effect of unfiltered *versus* filtered coffee (Tverdal et al., 2020). The consumption of decaffeinated coffee was also generally found to be associated with a lower risk of death, although the strength of this conclusion is limited by the fewer number of individuals consuming decaffeinated coffee (Ding et al., 2015; Freedman et al., 2012; Gardener et al., 2013; Je and Giovannucci, 2014; Loftfield et al., 2015; Park et al., 2017). Furthermore, the inverse association between coffee consumption and all-cause mortality was maintained irrespective of the caffeine content of coffee (Kim et al., 2019; Li et al., 2019) and irrespective of genetic polymorphisms causing slower or faster caffeine metabolism (Loftfield et al., 2018). This is highly suggestive of the participation of non-caffeine components in the benefits of coffee on lifespan. On the other hand, there is a tendency for a less robust association between lifespan and the consumption of decaffeinated compared to caffeinated coffee (Ding et al., 2015; Je and Giovannucci, 2014, but see Freedman et al., 2012; Gardener et al., 2013; Loftfield et al., 2015; Park et al., 2017) with decaffeinated coffee

consumption being associated with a smaller reduction in all-cause mortality (Lopez-Garcia et al., 2008; Torres-Collado et al., 2021). Additionally, it was demonstrated that caffeine consumption is directly associated with lifespan, exhibiting a U-shaped mortality curve (Feng et al., 2021; Mineharu et al., 2011; Paganini-Hill et al., 2007; Tsujimoto et al., 2017). This prompts the conclusion that both caffeine and non-caffeine components contribute to the benefits on lifespan of coffee consumption and future research should attempt to define if there is an additivity or even synergism between caffeine and presumably chlorogenic acids to bolster lifespan. Furthermore, the impact of other prominent coffee constituents with potential bioactive action, such as melanoidins, diterpenes or trigonelline in the aging process largely still remains to be studied (see Martel et al., 2019; Membrez et al., 2024; Neopane et al., 2023).

3. Impact of coffee intake on age-associated diseases contributing to mortality

The previously discussed ability of coffee to impact lifespan may result either from an ability of coffee intake to interfere with fundamental processes of aging or because the intake of coffee prevents some of the chronic diseases responsible for mortality. In Western countries where most epidemiological studies are carried out, the major causes of death are due to cardiovascular diseases often related to diabetes and obesity, as well as stroke, respiratory diseases and cancer (GBD, 2021 Causes of Death Collaborators, 2024). Notably, the regular intake of moderate doses of coffee is inversely associated with the incidence of most of these more prevalent diseases limiting lifespan (Grosso et al., 2017a; O'Keefe et al., 2013; Poole et al., 2017), as will be briefly discussed below (see also Fig. 1).

3.1. Cardiovascular diseases

There is robust evidence to support the contention that the regular intake of coffee is inversely associated with the incidence of different cardiovascular diseases, namely hypertension (Haghighatdoost et al., 2023; Mesas et al., 2011), arrhythmia (Bazal et al., 2021; Surma et al., 2023), ischemic brain diseases (Ding et al., 2014a; Park et al., 2023), as well as metabolic risk factors for cardiovascular diseases, such as metabolic syndrome (Wong et al., 2021), type 2 diabetes (Carlström and Larsson, 2018; Ding et al., 2014b; Osama et al., 2021; van Dam and Hu, 2005) or obesity (Lee et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2024b). Accordingly, most reviews and meta-analyses converge in the conclusion that coffee drinkers have a reduced risk specifically of cardiovascular mortality (Crippa et al., 2014; Di Maso et al., 2021; Grosso et al., 2016a; Kim et al., 2019; Malerba et al., 2013; O'Keefe et al., 2013; Zhou and Hyppönen, 2019), which is proposed to be a main contributor for the observed inverse relation between coffee consumption and mortality due to all causes in different cohorts (e.g. Abe et al., 2019; Ding et al., 2015; Kim et al., 2021; Lopez-Garcia et al., 2008). In general, as occurs for mortality due to all causes, the relation between coffee intake and cardiovascular mortality also follows a J-shaped curve with a maximal benefit observed at 2–3 cups of coffee (e.g. Kleemola et al., 2000; Lukic et al., 2020; Ruggiero et al., 2021). It is important to emphasize that although this inverse relation has a robust consistency, it has a low amplitude, i.e.

the protection afforded by coffee intake is modest when compared to other individual factors (see e.g. Arnett et al., 2019). However, the scientific evidence forces a complete inversion of the misconception initiated in the 60's that considered coffee consumption as a cardiovascular risk factor associated with coronary heart disease (Paul et al., 1963).

3.2. Stroke

Cerebrovascular diseases are the second most frequent cause of death and the leading cause of disability in an aged population in Europe (Prendes et al., 2024). Significant inverse associations were observed between coffee consumption and deaths attributed to stroke (Abe et al., 2019; Ding et al., 2015; Freedman et al., 2012; Gunter et al., 2017; Kim et al., 2021; Saito et al., 2015).

3.3. Respiratory diseases

Respiratory diseases are the third cause of death in European countries, leading to about 364,000 deaths in 2019 or 8 % of all deaths (The Lancet Respiratory Medicine, 2013). When analyzed, it was concluded that coffee consumption was inversely associated with mortality from respiratory diseases (Abe et al., 2019; Freedman et al., 2012; Kim et al., 2021; Lofffield et al., 2015; Saito et al., 2015).

3.4. Cancer

Cancer is also considered a major cause of death across all ages. Coffee intake was initially considered a risk factor for cancer, until in 2016 the International Agency for Research on Cancer finally used scientific criteria to evaluate the risk of coffee intake for the development of cancer, which is now classified in a group 3 as 'unclassifiable as to carcinogenicity in humans' (Alicandro et al., 2017; Loomis et al., 2016; Wang et al., 2016). This classification is still disputable at best, given that there is accumulating evidence documenting an inverse association of the intake of moderate doses of coffee with the incidence of some types of cancer, such as hepatocellular cancer (Bhurwal et al., 2020), melanoma (Micek et al., 2018) or colorectal cancer (Wang et al., 2020) and a possible decreased risk was found in some studies for oral/pharyngeal cancer (Wang et al., 2016), kidney cancer (Rhee et al., 2022) and for advanced prostate cancer (Chen et al., 2021). However, mixed data

Fig. 1. Coffee and its constituents (caffeine and chlorogenic acids) attenuate mortality and prevent the major causes of mortality in Western countries. Additionally, the regular intake of moderate doses of coffee also increases healthspan on aging by preventing the major causes of functional deterioration in the elderly. The Figure was generated with BioRender (licenced).

for other neoplasia suggest a lack of association of coffee intake with the incidence of lung cancer (Jin and Je, 2024), gastric cancer (Martimianaki et al., 2022), breast cancers (Nehlig et al., 2021), glioma (Pranata et al., 2022) or ovarian cancer (Shafiei et al., 2019) to name a few. Nevertheless, in the context of follow-up studies related to mortality, meta-analyses indicate that the consumption of coffee does seem to be associated with general cancer mortality (Crippa et al., 2014; Grosso et al., 2016a; Malerba et al., 2013), with inverse associations between coffee intake and all cancer mortality being reported in some cohorts (Grosso et al., 2017b; Kim et al., 2021; Sado et al., 2019; Tamakoshi et al., 2011), with minor benefits for some particular types of cancers (Di Maso et al., 2021; Jacobsen et al., 1986; Kim et al., 2019; Kunutsor et al., 2024) and a positive association with ovarian cancer mortality (Gunter et al., 2017).

4. Impact of coffee intake on healthspan upon aging

Apart from this conundrum of effects of coffee on lifespan and on chronic diseases contributing to mortality, there are parallel behavioral effects of coffee consumption that are not directly associated with lifespan but contribute to an increased healthspan on aging (Fig. 1). In fact, a recent study of 13,384 participants concluded that individuals with higher coffee consumption exhibited a younger biological age in relation to their chronological age, as indicated by lower mean advancements in PhenoAge and KDM-BA scores (Chen et al., 2024). This is of particular importance since the main translational goal of geroscience is not to increase longevity or lifespan, but instead to increase the quality of life of aged individuals (Olshansky, 2018).

4.1. Well-being and psychomotor performance

Although the definition of well-being is still solely based on subjective reporting, it is none the less interesting to note that healthy older adults habitually drinking coffee tend to report a heightened mood status and improved behavior upon intake of coffee or caffeine (Cropley et al., 2012; Kim et al., 2022; Kromhout et al., 2021; Swift and Tiplady, 1988; Yu et al., 1991); however, the association between coffee consumption and psychological well-being (mainly higher levels of optimism rather than of happiness) is rather weak (Qureshi et al., 2022). In healthy older adults caffeine intake increases psychomotor performance measures of attention (Bryant et al., 1998; Cropley et al., 2012; Sharma et al., 2022), in particular decreased attention upon mental fatigue or after stress loading (Baba et al., 2021; Smith et al., 2005). The comparison with younger adults suggests that old adults are more sensitive to the objective effects of caffeine while reporting less subjective effects than younger adults (Swift and Tiplady, 1988). Notably, caffeine intake counteracts the deterioration in aged volunteers of event-related potentials, which provides evidence for decreased levels of energy resources (Lorist et al., 1995). Additionally, caffeine ingestion positively enhances functional performance, manual dexterity and readiness to invest effort in healthy older adults (Duncan et al., 2014). This ability of caffeine to counteract the age-associated deterioration of sustained attention, reaction time and functional performance probably underlies the high prevalence of coffee consumption among the elderly (Samoggia and Riedel, 2019; Torres-Collado et al., 2018). But coffee consumption also affords benefits in other behavioral domains that contribute to healthspan upon aging (Massey, 1998; Takahashi and Ishigami, 2017), some of which will be subsequently discussed.

4.2. Cognition

Memory deterioration is amongst the most common concerns of aged adults (Jonker et al., 2000; Reid and MacLulich, 2006), probably due to the increased perception that the incidence of dementia increases exponentially with age from 65 years of age onwards (Cao et al., 2020; Jorm and Jolley, 1998). Several, but not all (Larsson and Orsini, 2018),

meta-analyses concluded that the regular consumption of coffee is inversely associated with the risk of developing dementia (Kim et al., 2015; Nila et al., 2023; Santos et al., 2010; Wu et al., 2017; Zhu et al., 2024) and in particular Alzheimer's disease (Liu et al., 2016). Some of these meta-analyses established a "J-shaped" association between coffee intake and incident cognitive disorders with a maximal effect obtained upon daily consumption of 2–3 cups of coffee, although the pooled odds ratios are suggestive of a rather modest association of coffee intake with the risk of cognitive disorders (Nila et al., 2023; Wu et al., 2017; Zhu et al., 2024). This modest benefit of coffee consumption on memory deterioration is probably the reason behind the heterogeneity of the conclusions of several studies probing the impact of coffee consumption during adulthood on the deterioration of memory with aging, with most studies finding a significant inverse association (Corley et al., 2010; Gardener et al., 2021; Hameleers et al., 2000; Iranpour et al., 2020; Mak et al., 2024; Paz-Graniel et al., 2021; van Gelder et al., 2007; Wu et al., 2011; Zhang et al., 2021b; Zhang et al., 2024a), whereas some studies report benefits only in women (Arab et al., 2011; Johnson-Kozlow et al., 2002; Ritchie et al., 2007) and others fail to reveal any significant relation (Laitala et al., 2009; Shirai et al., 2020). Whereas the long-term effects on memory of coffee intake during adulthood seem difficult to highlight, the regular consumption of coffee in community-based samples of older adults aged 80 or more years seems related to the preservation of cognitive function (Araújo et al., 2015; Johnson-Kozlow et al., 2002), in particular in aged individuals who considered themselves "morning types" (Ryan et al., 2002). However, augmenting coffee consumption in cognitively normal older individuals increases the rate of developing mild cognitive impairment, while preserving a constant moderate coffee consumption is associated to a reduced rate of the incidence of mild cognitive impairment (Solfrizzi et al., 2015). This better cognitive outcome of moderate coffee consumption in community-based aged individuals (69–86 years) with preserved cognition is particularly evident in relation to caffeine intake (Blum et al., 2024; Haller et al., 2018) and caffeine levels (Fu et al., 2023; Liu et al., 2023), with a particular benefit of caffeinated coffee while decaffeinated coffee was not associated with cognitive performance (Dong et al., 2020). This prompts the conclusion that caffeine may have greater benefits on cognitive performance in older adults than in young adults (Jarvis et al., 1993; Rogers and Dernoncourt, 1998). This may be related to the observation that a higher consumption of coffee is associated with slower accumulation of β -amyloid peptides (Gardener et al., 2021; Kim et al., 2019b), which occurs upon aging and has been considered a contributing factor for the development of Alzheimer's disease together with tau aggregates (e.g. Bloom, 2014). Moreover, increased levels of caffeine are associated with decreased amyloid positivity particularly in men (Zheng et al., 2023) and a significant positive correlation was found between the concentrations of the caffeine metabolite, theobromine both in the CSF and in the plasma, with β -amyloid peptides 1–42 in the cerebrospinal fluid (Travassos et al., 2015). Studies in human neuroblastoma cell lines also showed that coffee extracts, caffeine and other methylxanthines decreased the production of β -amyloid peptides (Fukuyama et al., 2018; Janitschke et al., 2019) and the aggregation of tau and β -amyloid peptides (Mancini et al., 2018; Tira et al., 2023). Furthermore, polymorphisms of adenosine A_{2A} receptors, the molecular target of caffeine and methylxanthines to afford neuroprotection (Cunha, 2016), are associated with the risk of Alzheimer's disease (Siokas et al., 2022) and with hippocampal volume in mild cognitive impairment and Alzheimer's disease (Horgusluoglu-Moloch et al., 2017). Polymorphisms of cytochrome P450 1A2 (CYP1A2 that define slower or faster caffeine metabolizers) influence the relation between coffee consumption and the risk of dementia (Lefèvre-Arbogast et al., 2024). Although these studies provide compelling evidence for the role of caffeine and methylxanthines on the preservation of cognition and decreased risk of dementia in the elderly, it should be emphasized that, as occurs for coffee intake, there is a rather modest impact of caffeine on cognitive decline upon aging, with even

opposite findings being reported by the same group in different cohorts that were interestingly associated with the deposition of Lewis bodies (Cornelis et al., 2022). It is also relevant to note that apart from caffeine, chlorogenic acids may also play a role in age-associated memory preservation upon coffee intake since several studies provided evidence that polyphenols, particularly chlorogenic acids, could affect memory performance in the elderly (e.g. Karademir et al., 2024; Ochiai et al., 2019; Saitou et al., 2018).

4.3. Depression

Depression is another major factor contributing to decreased healthspan upon aging. In fact, depression is prevalent in the elderly and is a major silent and overlooked mode of suffering in Western societies (Fiske et al., 2009; Hu et al., 2022). Different meta-analyses including cross-sectional and prospective studies converged on the conclusion that the regular consumption of coffee and dietary caffeine has a protective effect against the development of depression: those who reported the highest *versus* lowest levels of coffee intake were circa 25 % less likely to be depressed (Grosso et al., 2016c; Torabynasab et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2016b). The analysis of 146,566 participants from the UK Biobank revealed a J-shaped association between coffee consumption and the incidence of either depression or anxiety, with the lowest risk of these psychiatric disorders occurring at 2–3 cups per day (Min et al., 2023). This is in line with the ability of coffee intake to mitigate emotional responses to negative or stressful situations (Giles et al., 2018; Overstreet et al., 2018; Ratliff-Crain and Kane, 1995) and prompts the hypothesis that the previously discussed effects of coffee intake on cognitive deterioration may partly be due to a control of mood since mood deterioration contributes to the aggravation of dementia (Bennett and Thomas, 2014). The intake of coffee also increases in stressful conditions (Conway et al., 1981; Harris et al., 2007) and coffee intake triggers an increase in the levels of salivary α -amylase without a concomitant cortisol increase (Papakonstantinou et al., 2016), which suggests that coffee may have some anti-stress properties. Notably, the ability of regular intake of coffee to attenuate the perception of stress (Amendola et al., 1998; Lohi et al., 2007; Makki et al., 2023; Ullrich et al., 2015) is likely to be a central effect since coffee or caffeine intake/exposure is associated with increased plasma levels of cortisol, which is expected to sustain stress responses (al'Absi et al., 1998; Gavrieli et al., 2011; Hamer et al., 2006; Harris et al., 2007; Lovallo et al., 2006; Ping et al., 2012). Caffeinated coffee showed a more robust positive effect on mood compared with decaffeinated coffee with regular chlorogenic acid (Cropley et al., 2012), implying a particular role of caffeine in the control of mood. Accordingly, functional magnetic resonance imaging of volunteers performing an emotional face processing revealed that caffeine administration induced threat-related midbrain-periaqueductal gray activation while dampening the extent of threat-related amygdala activation and abolishing threat-related medial prefrontal cortex wall activation (Smith et al., 2012). Furthermore, polymorphisms of adenosine A_{2A} receptors are associated with depression (Oliveira et al., 2019) and panic disorders (e.g. Deckert et al., 1998; Hamilton et al., 2004) and the anti-parkinsonian A_{2A} receptor antagonist, istradefylline (Chen and Cunha, 2020) has a beneficial impact on mood (Nagayama et al., 2019). This main role of caffeine in the control of mood upon coffee intake is further heralded by the observations that decaffeinated coffee does not seem to be associated with the incidence of depression (Lucas et al., 2011; Min et al., 2023; but see Kimura et al., 2020) and that lower plasma levels of caffeine are associated with higher odds of major depressive disorder (Woolf et al., 2023). Apart from this relation with depression, the consumption of coffee is also related to the most life-threatening consequence of depression – suicide, which has an incidence in the elderly population larger than for younger adults (Sadek et al., 2024). Thus, regular and moderate caffeine intake reduces suicide ideation (Park et al., 2019) and the actual number of deaths attributed to suicide in studies carried out in

different continents (e.g. Ding et al., 2015; Kawachi et al., 1996; Klatsky et al., 1993; Smith, 2009; Tanskanen et al., 2000). In a pooled analysis of three large-scale US-based cohorts of middle-aged men and women, each additional two cups/day of coffee consumed was associated with a 25 % lower risk of suicide (Lucas et al., 2014). It still to be unraveled if the benefits afforded by coffee intake on the risk of suicide are only a consequence of its ability to control mood and depression or if it also involves other effects of coffee. It also remains to be studied if the effects of coffee intake on mood and suicide are more evident in the elderly rather than in younger adults.

4.4. Sleep

Sleep is a factor that is closely associated with mood and memory, given that insomnia severity and/or poor sleep quality predicts neuro-psychiatric symptoms (e.g. Hertenstein et al., 2019; Shi et al., 2018). As part of the natural aging process, sleep is modified through combined effects including modification of its circadian regulation (earlier sleep onset and earlier waking), of sleep structure (more fragmented and lighter with an increase in the number of EEG arousals), with a reduced homeostatic sleep pressure with increased frequency of daytime naps (e.g. Cooke and Ancoli-Israel, 2011; Crowley, 2011; Dijk et al., 2010; Li et al., 2018). There is considerable research documenting the impact of coffee intake, and of caffeine in particular, on sleep in adults (Clark and Landolt, 2017; Gardiner et al., 2023). However, the impact of coffee consumption on sleep in the elderly has been less explored and the results are somewhat conflicting probably as a result of most studies resorting to self-reporting rather than objective measures of sleep. Thus, some studies reported that caffeine-induced insomnia increased with aging in both men and women (Farazdaq et al., 2018; Frozi et al., 2018) although older women are more prone to report sleep disturbances (McGhie and Russell, 1962). In contrast, other studies in community-dwelling elderly (2673 men and 3213 women aged 65 years and older) showed that caffeine intake was associated with a lower number of insomnia symptoms (Jaussent et al., 2011). Also, there is a lower reported coffee consumption and lower plasma caffeine concentrations in the community-dwelling elderly of both sexes who reported the poorest sleep quality (Curless et al., 1993). Accordingly, amongst the 1256 participants aged 61–101 years in community-dwelling older males and females from the Longitudinal Ageing Study Amsterdam, older females who abstained from caffeine consumption reported a shorter sleep duration whereas no associations were observed in older males (van der Linden et al., 2023). Notably, the average sleep duration measured by actigraphy and the average caffeine intake were not significantly correlated (Hu et al., 2020), further arguing for a more discrete impact of coffee and caffeine intake on sleep in the elderly compared to younger adults. Also, the relation between sleep homeostasis and the intake of coffee and caffeine in particular, seems different in the elderly as it was observed that a shorter sleep duration predicted a stronger tendency to consume caffeine, and this phenomenon is only found in middle-aged but not in older adults, implying that using caffeine to compensate for sleep loss is a habit of middle-aged adults rather than of the elderly (Hu et al., 2020). Also, Landolt's group (Landolt et al., 2012) reported that the effects of sleep deprivation and caffeine on regional theta power and vigilant attention are inversely correlated across older and younger age groups and are dependent on polymorphisms of the adenosine A_{2A} receptor gene, the putative molecular target of caffeine in the brain (IJerman et al., 2022). Thus, the available evidence questions the assumption that the regular intake of moderate amounts of coffee may curtail sleep length and homeostasis in the elderly as it was concluded in younger adults (Clark and Landolt, 2017). Furthermore, it also remains to be studied if caffeine will also be effective in the elderly to counteract the deleterious effects of poor sleep quality on well-being and health, as it does in younger adults (Gardiner et al., 2023).

4.5. Sensory deterioration

Sensory deterioration is prevalent in the elderly and a major contributor to social distancing impacting their neuropsychiatric status; thus, *vision* undergoes a deterioration upon aging (Crews and Campbell, 2004) and caffeine administration in adults bolsters dynamic visual acuity (Redondo et al., 2021), increasing reading rate and tear film quality without long-term effects on perceptual surround suppression (Nguyen et al., 2018), although this has not been tested in aged adults. The regular consumption of coffee also prevents neurodegeneration in the eye, as heralded by optical coherence tomography studies showing that the consumption of 2–3 cups of coffee per day is significantly associated with an increased macular retinal nerve fiber layer thickness, an inverse marker of neurodegeneration, in a population-based cohort study in middle-aged adults (40–69 years old at the time of recruitment) (Yuan et al., 2023). Accordingly, coffee intake seems to attenuate the incidence of some of the major causes of visual impairment in the elderly: thus, cataract blindness was found to be significantly lower in groups consuming higher amounts of coffee in comparison to the groups with lower coffee intake (Varma et al., 2016) and the prevalence of vision-threatening diabetic retinopathy showed a significantly decreasing tendency according to daily coffee consumption (Lee et al., 2022). There is conflicting evidence for glaucoma (c.f. Bae et al., 2020; Kim et al., 2021b), probably because caffeine increases intraocular pressure in healthy adults (Avisar et al., 2002) without expectable clinical impact (Jiwani et al., 2012), but significantly increased intraocular pressure in patients with glaucoma or ocular hypertension (Li et al., 2011), which could exacerbate glaucomatous optic neurodegeneration (Chandrasekaran et al., 2005; Okuno et al., 2002; Yilmaz Tugan et al., 2022).

In contrast to the expected benefits for the preservation of vision upon coffee consumption on aging, the effects of coffee intake on *hearing* are contradictory, with some cohorts revealing a higher prevalence of hearing loss associated with coffee consumption (Wu et al., 2023b), others reporting that urinary caffeine metabolites are not associated with the hearing threshold shifts in US adults (Long and Tang, 2021) and others indicating a protective effect of the regular intake of moderate doses of coffee on hearing loss and tinnitus (Lee et al., 2018; see also Figueiredo et al., 2021; Glicksman et al., 2014; Machado-Fragua et al., 2021). Of note, noise-induced hearing loss in workers is less frequent in coffee consumers (Chang and Chang, 2009), although caffeine is an aggravating factor of Meniere's disease (Sánchez-Sellero et al., 2018). Since hearing deterioration has been linked to an increased susceptibility to develop dementia (Wilroth et al., 2024), it will be of interest in future studies to clarify the impact of coffee and of caffeine in age-associated hearing loss.

Although *olfactory* deterioration (hyposmia and anosmia) is also associated with neurodegenerative disorders (Barresi et al., 2012; Rahayel et al., 2012), there is sparse research in humans relating the consumption of coffee with olfaction. Thus, in first-degree relatives of Parkinson's disease patients, olfactory function was higher for those who consumed more caffeine (Siderowf et al., 2007). When testing caffeine administration in healthy adults, one study found no effect on a group of normal (Fjaeldstad and Fernandes, 2020) or hyposmic individuals (Meusel et al., 2016), another found no differences in odor function (Han et al., 2020) and a third study reported that caffeine enhanced odor sensitivity but reduce odor identification in non-coffee consumers, being devoid of overall effect on odor function in coffee consumers (Stafford and Orgill, 2020). There are no available data in elderly individuals.

Even less is known about the eventual effects of coffee consumption on *taste* perception, which declines during the healthy aging process (Methven et al., 2012). Thus, by applying tests for olfactory and gustatory sensitivity before and after coffee intake, it was concluded that coffee (regular and decaffeinated) alters the subsequent perception of taste, specifically by increasing the sensitivity to sweet and decreasing

the sensitivity to bitter (Fjaeldstad and Fernandes, 2020). In summary, in spite of some indications that the regular consumption of coffee might format the sustainability of different sensory systems upon aging, there seems to be a need to experimentally tackle this question to provide clear answers on the effects of coffee and caffeine intake on sensory function specifically in the elderly.

4.6. Frailty

In contrast to these still unclear connections between coffee intake and sensory perception, there is robust and consistent evidence linking the regular consumption of caffeine with physical health in the elderly. Frailty, understood as a functional deterioration resulting from the parallel loss of bone and muscle tissue (sarcopenia), is a main contributor to limiting the mobility and autonomy of the elderly, together with an increased risk of accidents and fractures (Sternberg et al., 2011). Although the objective definition of frailty is still problematic (Gagesch et al., 2022), several studies have investigated the impact of coffee intake on different endpoints associated with frailty; it is observed that higher exposure to coffee drinking is strongly associated with better physical functioning outcomes (Jyväkorpi et al., 2021; Mazeaud et al., 2022), decreased sarcopenia (Chung et al., 2017; Kawakami et al., 2023; Kim and Park, 2017; Lee and Shin, 2023) and reduced odds of physical frailty (Chua et al., 2023; Pang et al., 2023). Additionally, different meta-analyses concluded that the regular intake of moderate doses of coffee affords protective effects against osteoporosis/osteopenia (Ye et al., 2024; Zhang et al., 2024b), the risk of falls (Machado-Fragua et al., 2019) and the risk of fractures in the elderly (Asoudeh et al., 2023; Chen et al., 2023; Xu and Zhai, 2024; Zeng et al., 2022; but see Lee et al., 2014). Overall, this increased musculoskeletal preservation associated with coffee intake is likely related to the inverse associations between coffee intake and deaths due to injury and accidents (Abe et al., 2019; Freedman et al., 2012; Saito et al., 2015).

5. Impact of coffee on mechanisms associated with aging

The previously discussed ability of coffee and caffeine intake to dampen the most frequent causes of death in Western population (Fig. 1) suggests that coffee intake is interfering with a single risk factor for all age-associated chronic diseases rather than affecting each age-associated chronic disease by different mechanisms. Furthermore, the ability of coffee intake to ameliorate several features limiting the quality of life upon aging rather than only controlling the incidence of diseases contributing to define lifespan, is an additional argument to support the contention that coffee intake may affect fundamental mechanisms governing the aging process. The establishment of a mechanistic basis for the impact of coffee intake on age-related well-being and diseases is also critical to exclude the possibility that the epidemiological links may be indirectly due to factors associated to coffee intake rather than to the effects of coffee. For instance, one could conceive that people who drink 3 cups of coffee a day spend more time socializing and this may be the key factor to bolster their wellbeing and decrease the incidence of the different age-related diseases. Alternatively, it could be that people who can afford to drink 3 cups a day of higher quality coffee are richer, and their economic wealth may be the key factor promoting their well-being and protecting their health. The need to clarify a mechanism of action to provide a rationale for the direct benefit of coffee intake to increase healthspan on aging, should justify reviewing the current evidence linking coffee and caffeine intake with the pillars of aging (Fig. 2; Kennedy et al., 2014), focusing on humans and human tissues.

5.1. Coffee consumption and macromolecular damage

Throughout lifetime, cells are exposed to several exogenous and endogenous stressors, such as environmental toxins, ultraviolet radiation or the production of radical species that can alter the integrity and

Fig. 2. Coffee and its constituents (caffeine and chlorogenic acids) impact of the major biological mechanisms associated with aging, attenuating genomic instability, macromolecular damage, metabolic and proteostatic impairments, with particularly robust effects on the control of stress adaptation and inflammation and unclear effects on stem cells and regeneration. The Figure was generated with BioRender (licenced).

stability of DNA, leading to genomic instability; in this context, excessive DNA damage or insufficient DNA repair favors the aging process (Lombard et al., 2005; Richardson and Schadt, 2014; Vijg and Suh, 2013). The relation between coffee consumption and genetic instability has, so far, only been investigated in intervention studies in healthy young participants. Thus, the consumption during one month of moderate doses of coffee or cocoa-based products containing caffeine, decreased the plasma levels of different markers of DNA damage (8-OH-2'-deoxy-guanosine, 8-OH-guanine, and 8-NO₂-cGMP) in young healthy volunteers (Martini et al., 2021). Accordingly, in 84 healthy adult men, the daily consumption during 4 weeks of 750 mL of fresh coffee (compared to water) significantly ($p = 0.0002$) decreased by 27 % the extent of spontaneous DNA strand breaks assessed by comet assay in blood cells (Bakuradze et al., 2015). A similar decrease in total DNA strand breaks was observed in isolated lymphocytes in another intervention study after intake of moderate doses of instant coffee (Hoelzl et al., 2010). In further human intervention studies, coffee consumption was reported to protect against DNA damage in lymphocytes induced by genotoxic compounds (Bichler et al., 2007; Mišfk et al., 2010; Steinkellner et al., 2005). In contrast, a heavier coffee consumption of more than 3 cups of coffee per day increased sperm DNA damage associated with double-strand DNA breaks (Schmid et al., 2007). Studies *in vitro* in human cells or tissues also reported an ability of coffee extracts rich in caffeoylquinic acids as well as *Robusta* spent coffee extract, to protect against oxidation and DNA damage (29–73 % protection by comet assay) induced by hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) in HeLa cells (Bravo et al., 2013). Likewise, in a preclinical accelerated aging model of human skin (fragments cultured for 3 days in serum-free medium) it was shown that 200 μM caffeine counteracted the epidermal accumulation of the DNA-damage marker γH2A.X (van Lessen et al., 2024). This is apparently the only study investigating a putative protective effect of coffee intake on genomic instability related to aging, which implies the need to investigate in elderly volunteers if the consumption of coffee indeed affords a protection against age-associated genomic instability. It should also be noted that, as occurs in the intervention studies, the apparent protective effect of coffee/caffeine is lost when testing high levels of caffeine, which are genotoxic (D'Ambrosio, 1994; Pincheira and

López-Sáez, 1991; Stoilov et al., 1994).

Telomeres are nucleoprotein structures at the chromosome ends protecting genomic DNA from end-to-end fusion. Telomeres tendentially become shorter with cell division consequently triggering cellular senescence, although this is a potentially reversible dynamic process through enzymatic action of telomerase reverse transcriptase (TERT); thus, telomere shortening or damage is considered a hallmark of aging and is associated with the incidence of several chronic diseases (Cawthon et al., 2003; Epel et al., 2008). The first suggestion that coffee consumption might be associated with telomere length was obtained in a cross-over intervention study in 40 patients with chronic hepatitis C, where it was concluded that telomere length was significantly higher in patients during coffee intake (Cardin et al., 2013). Observational studies have provided conflicting evidence, with some reporting that the consumption of 2–3 cups of coffee daily is significantly associated with longer telomeres in leukocytes of 4780 women included in the Nurses' Health Study (Liu et al., 2016), whereas leukocyte telomere length was found not to be significantly associated with coffee intake after adjustment for age and energy either in a multi-ethnic cohort (Nettleton et al., 2008) or in 1638 controls in the Prostate, Lung, Colorectal, and Ovarian Cancer Screening Trial (Steiner et al., 2020). A follow up study of 1952 healthy adults for 6 years also failed to detect an association between coffee intake and telomere length (Sohn et al., 2023). Finally, observational analyses of 468,924 participants from the UK Biobank suggested a different impact of different types of coffee, with the intake of instant coffee but not filtered coffee, being negatively correlated with telomere length (Wei et al., 2023). When analyzing the association between caffeine intake and telomere length, the findings are also conflicting. Even within the same cohort of the National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey different studies offered opposite conclusions, one reporting that caffeine consumption was inversely related to telomere length in 5826 adults (Tucker, 2017) and another reporting that caffeine intake decreased across telomere quarters in 10,568 participants (Mazidi et al., 2017). Interestingly, caffeine intake by the mothers was significantly and positively associated with longer fetal telomere length (Griffin et al., 2020) and studies *in vitro* in HeLa cells found that caffeine promoted the expression of telomerase reverse transcriptase (TERT) at both mRNA and protein levels, and consequently extended telomere length and prevented cellular senescence (Tao et al., 2021). These conflicting results prompt the need to confirm if there might indeed be an association of coffee intake with telomere length specifically in elderly populations with adequately powered randomized controlled trials.

5.2. Coffee consumption and epigenetic modifications

The established relation between epigenetic deregulation and the aging process (Lu et al., 2023) allowed defining epigenetic clocks (e.g. Horvath and Raj, 2018; Jylhävä et al., 2017; Shireby et al., 2020) prompting the exploration of the relation between the regular consumption of coffee and epigenetic alterations as a proxy of the aging process. Initial studies in blood immune cells revealed that habitual coffee consumption was associated with significant alterations of the methylation levels of six CpG sites that are located within 1500 base pairs of transcription factor binding and transcriptional start sites of protein kinase genes (Chuang et al., 2017), although another study failed to identify significant epigenetic alterations in coffee consumers (Ek et al., 2017). A subsequent epigenome-wide association study in 15,789 participants revealed that regular coffee consumption altered the methylation pattern of 11 CpG sites, which annotated to the AHRR, F2RL3, FLJ43663, HDAC4, GFI1 and PHGDH genes, the latter related to the risk of fatty liver disease (Karabegović et al., 2021). Such studies will hopefully confirm in humans the ability of caffeine to epigenetically control network of genes related to memory and to metabolic control (Paiva et al., 2022). Most importantly, a recent study provided evidence that coffee intake was associated with reduced levels of epigenetic

aging, normalizing the pattern of DNA methylation in the Skin&Blood clock that seems to be the most accurate predictor of chronological age in blood samples of over 1000 participants (Noroozi et al., 2024).

In vitro studies in human cell lines defined the ability of different coffee constituents, namely caffeine and chlorogenic acids, to affect the epigenome in cellular models (Ding et al., 2023). Thus, the treatment of human adrenocortical cell line NCI-H295A with 4 or 40 μM caffeine for 48 hours resulted in a decreased frequency of methylation of a single CpG site at nt-682 of the StAR promoter (Ping et al., 2012). In parallel, the treatment of Jurkat and HL-60 cells with 100 μM 5-O-(trans-3,4-dihydroxycinnamoyl)-D-quinic acid (a chlorogenic acid present in coffee) for 72 hours significantly decreased the levels of 5-mC in Jurkat cells but not in HL-60 cells, whereas 100 μM 3-(3,4-dihydroxycinnamoyl)quinic acid (another chlorogenic acid present in coffee) did not alter the levels of 5-mC in either cell types (Hernandes et al., 2020).

Although these initial studies tentatively relate coffee intake with alterations of the epigenome and the epigenetic clock, future studies should explore if this association is present in cells of different organs and tissues that are differently affected upon aging. This should be accompanied by *in vitro* studies to attempt tackling the molecular mechanisms underlying this apparent ability of coffee intake to normalize the epigenetic aging clock.

5.3. Coffee consumption and metabolic dysfunction

Metabolic dysfunction in aging encompasses two intertwined groups of dynamic processes occurring at different integrative levels, namely the regulation of metabolic resources throughout the body (glycemia, lipidemia and proteinemia) and the regulation of the utilization of carbon-based energy sources by cells (primary metabolism). Coffee and its components can modulate both groups of processes that tend to deteriorate upon aging, thus making these effects of coffee rather tempting mechanisms to underlie the ability of coffee intake to preserve healthspan upon aging.

The regular intake of coffee tends to increase fasting glucose plasma levels and glucose tolerance although reducing insulin sensitivity (e.g. Hiramatsu et al., 2013; Reis et al., 2018; Shi et al., 2016; but see Lecoultre et al., 2014; Rakvaag et al., 2016; Sarriá et al., 2018), but these effects seem to be at least balanced by the ability of regular (not acute) coffee intake to normalize the plasma levels of triglycerides and of LDL (Kempf et al., 2010; Ramli et al., 2021). This probably results from the ability of coffee intake to increase resting metabolic activity by 6–12 % in healthy or obese adults (Acheson et al., 1980; Alshahrani et al., 2023; Bracco et al., 1995), which mainly results from increased fat utilization (Haffner et al., 1985). The targets of caffeine – adenosine receptors, namely the adenosine A_1 receptor subtype plays a central role in the health benefits afforded by ketogenic diets (Ruskin et al., 2020), but it still remains to be tested if and how caffeinated coffee intake might affect this alternative pathway of lipid energetic utilization (Baumeister et al., 2021). Further evidence suggests that coffee consumption increases the levels of leptin and ghrelin, which regulate appetite, satiety, and energy metabolism (Zhang and Zhang, 2018; Ochoa-Rosales et al., 2023; Osama et al., 2021; Sarriá et al., 2020; but see Simental-Mendía et al., 2023) and there is a striking ability of caffeine to induce a conversion of white into brown fat (Velickovic et al., 2019), which is expected to bolster metabolic homeostasis (Scheele and Wolfrum, 2020). However, this ability of coffee intake to impact the whole-body management of metabolic resources still remains to be characterized in the elderly. In aged subjects, coffee consumption lowers the plasma levels of triglycerides (Ghavami et al., 2021; Grosso et al., 2015; Zhao et al., 2024; but see Du et al., 2020) and increases post-load rather than fasting glucose and insulin (Hiltunen, 2006; van Dam et al., 2004; Yarmolinsky et al., 2015). Moreover, the regular consumption of coffee displays a tendency for an association with a lower risk of metabolic syndrome (Corbi-Cobo-Losey et al., 2023; Marventano et al., 2016; Ramli et al., 2021; Shin et al., 2019; Tsai et al., 2023; Watanabe et al., 2023, but see

Wong et al., 2022; Kim et al., 2014) and with a robust prevention of type 2 diabetes (Carlström and Larsson, 2018; Ding et al., 2014b; Osama et al., 2021; van Dam and Hu, 2005). The protection afforded by regular coffee intake against these metabolic diseases is a compelling argument for the ability of coffee intake to prevent metabolic dysfunction, but there is still the need to unveil the underlying mechanisms to provide a direct demonstration of the ability of coffee consumption to prevent metabolic dysfunction upon aging.

One mechanism underlying this putative ability of coffee intake to control metabolic imbalance upon aging might be related to the emerging evidence indicating an ability of coffee components to modify the activity of the main metabolic regulators within cells, namely AMPK, which is centrally associated with cellular aging (Cetrullo et al., 2015; Yu et al., 2021). Thus, the exposure of human hepatoma HepG2 cells to an aqueous extract of bioactive compounds from coffee triggers several metabolic adaptive features in this cell line modeling the organ mainly responsible for metabolic control – the liver, namely an increased activity of carnitine palmitoyltransferase-1 activity (1.3–1.7-fold) by activating AMPK, together with increased expression of glucose transporters type 2 (GLUT2) coupled to increased glucose uptake and glucokinase activity (Rebollo-Hernanz et al., 2022). Also, cells exposed to *Robusta* coffee silverskin extract display altered activities of AMPK, sirtuin-1 and mTOR (Hayes et al., 2023). Some of the main coffee components can individually affect the activity of AMPK, as best heralded by the parallel ability of caffeine (Quan et al., 2013) and of chlorogenic acids (Ma et al., 2023) to control lipid accumulation through AMPK in HepG2 cells, the latter synergizing with metformin (Namvarjah et al., 2022), a proposed anti-aging drug (Glossmann and Lutz, 2019). Chlorogenic acids also promote AMPK phosphorylation in immortalized human oral keratinocytes challenged with lipopolysaccharide (Song et al., 2022) and caffeine (50 μM) activates AMPK causing enhanced migration of human umbilical vein endothelial cells (Tsai et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2021). Coffee intake is further associated with the activation of another group of intracellular metabolic coordinators of primary metabolism and epigenetics – sirtuins, which are argued to play a key role in managing cellular stress and the aging process (Cetrullo et al., 2015; Yu et al., 2021; Zhao et al., 2020). The daily consumption of coffee by healthy volunteers of both sexes significantly increases serum levels of sirtuin-1 (Gonçálinho et al., 2022), in agreement with the ability of chlorogenic acids to recruit sirtuin-1 to prevent palmitate-induced lipotoxicity in a non-transformed hepatocyte AML12 cell line (Yang et al., 2019) or in endothelial cells (Tsai et al., 2018) and with the ability of caffeine to activate sirtuin-1 in primary adipose-derived stem cells (Su et al., 2013) and to bind and activate sirtuin-3 in immortalized human keratinocytes (Xu et al., 2020). Although this evidence constitutes compelling arguments to propose that coffee intake may restore metabolic dysfunction upon aging through the normalization of the activity of AMPK and sirtuins, the truth is that this hypothesis still remains to be experimentally tested in aging cells and aged individuals.

Another candidate mechanism recurrently presented as being central to understanding the ability of regular coffee intake to attenuate age-related processes is linked to mitochondria dysfunction and generation of free radicals (Balaban et al., 2005; Cui et al., 2012; Dai et al., 2014). There is associative and causative evidence that mitochondria dysfunction is present and can trigger cellular aging (Kauppila et al., 2017; Sun et al., 2016) and there have been some attempts to explore whether coffee or coffee components might directly affect mitochondria to prevent mitochondria dysfunction. Thus, coffee extracts enhance respiration and ATP production via peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor co-activator 1 alpha (PGC-1 α), with an increased expression of oxidative phosphorylation complexes in HepG2 cells (Rebollo-Hernanz et al., 2022). Caffeine can also affect mitochondria functioning (Momtaz et al., 2021), which may involve a combination of direct effects through binding of caffeine to cyclin-dependent kinase inhibitor 1B/p27 (Ale-Agha et al., 2018) or adenosine

receptor-mediated control of transducing pathways impacting on mitochondria function (Castro et al., 2020; Cunha, 2016; Ferrante et al., 2016; Tamura et al., 2012). Furthermore, caffeine can affect mitochondria fusion/fission through dynamin-related protein 1 (Drp1), the master regulator of mitochondrial fission (Wang et al., 2021), and mitochondria biogenesis through induction of PGC-1 α , an essential precursor to mitochondrial biosynthesis (Vaughan et al., 2012). Additionally, chlorogenic acids may also directly affect mitochondria (Zhou et al., 2016) and increase the activity of mitochondrial enzymes, including citrate synthase, isocitrate dehydrogenase, and malate dehydrogenase, which are part of the tricarboxylic acid cycle, and upregulate proteins involved in the electron transport system (Takahashi et al., 2022). In AML12 cells, a non-transformed hepatocyte cell line, chlorogenic acids also increased mitochondrial mass and mitochondrial membrane potential by attenuating mitochondrial fragmentation by inhibiting dynamin-related protein 1 (Drp1) and enhancing mitofusin-2 expression (Yang et al., 2019).

These effects not only rebalance mitochondria bioenergetics but also attenuate the production of radical oxygen species (ROS) as a result of mitochondria dysfunction. Oxidative stress is frequently considered a main culprit of several age-related chronic diseases and of the aging process (Kauppila et al., 2017; Sun et al., 2016). The combined evidence that coffee consumption affords protection against age-associated chronic diseases that are generally assumed to have a contribution from oxidative stress (e.g. stroke, cardiovascular disease, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, Alzheimer's disease, diabetes) together with the *in vitro* observations that coffee components, namely chlorogenic acids (Baeza et al., 2014; Victoria-Montesinos et al., 2021; Yao et al., 2019; Zang et al., 2003) and caffeine (Li et al., 2018; Metro et al., 2017; Özs et al., 2022; Xu et al., 2020) can dampen the production of free radicals in *in vitro* systems, was probably the basis for the generalization of the concept that the benefits of coffee intake on human health might essentially result from an antioxidant effect of coffee. Although this is certainly a tempting hypothesis, the *in vivo* studies have still largely produced inconclusive experimental evidence (Dludla et al., 2023; Martini et al., 2016; Wang et al., 2023). In fact, some observational and intervention epidemiological studies showed that the regular (chronic) consumption of coffee increases the antioxidant potential assessed through different markers in the blood of adult volunteers (Agudelo-Ochoa et al., 2016; Chen and Kotani, 2015; Corrêa et al., 2012; Ishizaka et al., 2013; Katada et al., 2018; Kotyczka et al., 2011; Martínez-López et al., 2019; Teekachunhatean et al., 2012), but other studies failed to confirm this conclusion (Hoelzl et al., 2010; Mišík et al., 2010; Revuelta-Iniesta and Al-Dujaili, 2014; Shaposhnikov et al., 2018). Similarly, the impact of chronic coffee consumption was also reported to modulate endogenous antioxidant systems (catalase, superoxide dismutase, glutathione peroxidase) in some studies (Bakuradze et al., 2011; Corrêa et al., 2012; Kotyczka et al., 2011), but not in others (Hoelzl et al., 2010; Mišík et al., 2010; Mursu et al., 2005; Teekachunhatean et al., 2012) with no clear modification of the levels of glutathione (Hoelzl et al., 2010; Kotyczka et al., 2011; Mišík et al., 2010; Teekachunhatean et al., 2012). Chronic coffee intake also produces inconsistent effects on serum or urine biomarkers of oxidative damage of lipids (malondialdehyde, oxidized LDL, isoprostanes, oxystrols; Katada et al., 2018; Kempf et al., 2010; Lara-Guzmán et al., 2021; Martínez-López et al., 2019; Yukawa et al., 2004; but see Corrêa et al., 2012; Martini et al., 2021; Mišík et al., 2010; Mursu et al., 2005; Shaposhnikov et al., 2018; Teekachunhatean et al., 2012), proteins (3-nitrotyrosine; Hoelzl et al., 2010; but see Kempf et al., 2010; Mišík et al., 2010) and DNA oxidative damage (8-OHdG; Bakuradze et al., 2011, 2014; Cardin et al., 2013; Hori et al., 2014; Mišík et al., 2010; but see Martini et al., 2021; Shaposhnikov et al., 2018). This disparity between the benefits afforded by coffee intake against different age-associated chronic diseases and the inability to provide clear evidence for a mechanistic link between coffee intake and oxidative stress adds to the largely disappointing results of antioxidant supplementation clinical trials (Dai et al.,

2014), contributing to question the clinical relevance of oxidative stress in human diseases. Furthermore, there is (still) limited evidence on the role of coffee-mediated control of oxidative stress to control senescence. Thus, observational studies in elderly participants, reported an ability of regular coffee consumption to control oxidative stress (Lopes Boschetti et al., 2023), lipid peroxidation (Kempf et al., 2010) and biomarkers of oxidative DNA damage (Cardin et al., 2013). Additionally, *in vitro* studies revealed an ability of caffeine to control senescence markers (increased p21 levels and reduced levels of eNOS and thioredoxin-1) through a normalized redox balance in senescent human endothelial cells (Merk et al., 2023), as well as an ability of chlorogenic acid to control H₂O₂-induced senescence in human umbilical vein endothelial cells through the nuclear factor erythroid 2-factor 2 (Nrf2)/HO-1 pathway (Hada et al., 2020). Thus, although promising, this preliminary evidence will require additional experimental efforts to establish the dampening oxidative stress as a mechanism underlying the benefits of regular coffee consumption on the preservation of healthspan upon aging.

5.4. Coffee consumption and proteostasis

Protein homeostasis – designed as proteostasis – is an essential process that maintains protein structure and function. Proteostasis imbalance can be a result of cellular damage such as oxidative stress, when many proteins become insoluble and accumulate in a wide variety of tissues (Aman et al., 2021; Campisi et al., 2019), leading to age-related diseases such as Alzheimer's and Parkinson's diseases (Wong and Cuervo, 2010), sarcopenia (Musci et al., 2018) and atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease (Gouveia et al., 2017) to name a few. These proteostatic impairments observed in the aging process can involve molecular chaperones, the proteasome, as well as the process of autophagy (Kaushik and Cuervo, 2015). The decline in or inhibition of autophagy is associated with senescence and premature aging and, conversely, activation of autophagy inhibits stress-induced cellular senescence and prevents premature aging, improving healthspan (Cuervo et al., 2005; Rubinsztein et al., 2011). Accumulating evidence in different models prompts the conclusion that the regular intake of coffee or chronic exposure to moderate doses/concentrations of caffeine *in vivo* and *in vitro* activates autophagy flux via inhibition of mTOR signaling (Ray, 2013; Takahashi and Ishigami, 2017). Although some of the studies on this topic (e.g. Gibbs et al., 2015; Saiki et al., 2011; Tripathi et al., 2022; Zhan et al., 2010) used concentrations of caffeine that are never attained in living individuals (>0.5 mM), some other excellent studies tested physiologically relevant concentrations of caffeine. One study (Li et al., 2018) used an *in vitro* model of human keratinocytes to show that a low concentration of caffeine (<10 μ M) suppresses cellular senescence and skin damage by activation of autophagy through a series of sequential events, starting from the inhibition of its primary cellular target adenosine A_{2A} receptors to increase the protein levels of sirtuin-3 and activate a major metabolic coordinator and regulator of mTOR and AMPK. Another elegant study showed that the topical treatment of human dermal fibroblasts with *Coffea arabica* seed plant extracts bolstered the ubiquitin-proteasome and autophagy process, as assessed by an increased proteasome activity and reduction of protein carbonylation, of lipofuscin levels and of autophagy related 7 (Atg7) and mTOR gene expression (Biscaro et al., 2022). This ability of coffee/caffeine to bolster protein turnover may underlie the observation that the regular consumption of moderate doses of coffee decreases the age-related alteration of the plasma protein profile to reduce the predicted biological aging (Enroth et al., 2015). However, this tentative relation between coffee/caffeine and the control of proteostasis still has to be consolidated not only by using physiological concentrations of caffeine but also by extending these studies to coffee and testing different regimens and different types of coffee and especially monitoring coffee-induced alterations of proteostasis in elderly individuals. Finally, it would be relevant to investigate if the effect of coffee is mostly attributable to

caffeine or if coffee-containing chlorogenic acids might also control any of the different processes involved in the imbalance of proteostasis.

5.5. Coffee consumption and inflammation

Aging is associated with an increased number of senescent cells (Tuttle et al., 2021) that produce a senescence-associated secretory response (SASP) composed of growth factors (e.g. transforming growth factor- β (TGF- β)), chemokines, proteases procoagulant factors, extracellular matrix proteases (e.g. matrix metalloproteinases) and proinflammatory cytokines (such as interleukin-1 β and interleukin-6) to attract immune cells to remove these senescent cells by phagocytosis to restore homeostasis (Franceschi et al., 2018; Munoz-Espin and Serrano, 2014; Tchkonina et al., 2013). The accumulation of senescent cells characteristic of the aging process leads to an over-production of SASP producing a chronic inflammation called “inflammaging” that contributes to the dysfunction and damage of tissues namely in age-associated chronic diseases (Ferrucci and Fabbri, 2018; Franceschi and Campisi, 2014).

Notably, the prolonged intake of coffee seems associated with a reduction of subclinical inflammation (Bhattacharya, 2017; Dlugda et al., 2023, Surma et al., 2023), although this relation has been questioned in some reviews (Moua et al., 2020; Paiva et al., 2019). In fact, large cross-sectional surveys carried out in different geographical localizations and enrolling tens to hundreds of thousand middle-aged healthy men and women suggest that the regular consumption of moderate doses of coffee tends to decrease basal inflammatory status (e.g. Gunter et al., 2017; Hang et al., 2019; Maki et al., 2010; Schulze et al., 2005). Cohorts including younger individuals tend to find a negative impact of coffee intake on plasma inflammatory markers (Zampelas et al., 2004) and this relation is particularly robust in elderly individuals (Kotani et al., 2008; Pham et al., 2011). A meta-analysis focusing on the plasma levels of C-reactive protein confirmed a particular association of coffee intake with plasma high-sensitivity C-reactive protein (hsCRP) rather than with standard C-reactive protein (Zhang and Zhang, 2018; see also Moua et al., 2020). More recent studies with more sensitive and selective analytical procedures to quantify plasma high-sensitivity C-reactive protein in 9337 middle-aged adult subjects (20–65 years old) found an inverse association both in men and women consuming 2–3 cups of black coffee (Odds Ratio = 0.61, 95 % CI: 0.45–0.84), which was weaker in those consuming coffee with sugar and/or cream (Choi and Je, 2023). A similar inverse association between coffee consumption and other plasma inflammatory markers such as interleukin-6 and soluble tumor necrosis factor receptor-2 was also concluded in 2 cohorts of 15,551 women and 7397 men (Hang et al., 2019), confirming previous findings with other plasma markers of inflammation (Schulze et al., 2005) such as interleukin-18 (Kempf et al., 2010) and E-selectin (Lopez-Garcia et al., 2006).

There also seems to be an association between the regular consumption of moderate doses of coffee and the incidence of inflammatory diseases. The association of coffee intake with inflammation was first noted in 41,836 women aged 55–69 years who were followed for 15 years, where it was found that the hazard ratio for death from inflammatory diseases was 0.72 (95 % CI: 0.55–0.93) for consumption of 1–3 cups/day (Andersen et al., 2006). In particular, in inflammatory bowel disease, coffee intake as well as total caffeine intake is inversely associated with the risk of ulcerative colitis with an adjusted odds ratio of 0.44 between extreme quartiles (Tanaka et al., 2024), as also observed in other prospective cohort studies (Wu et al., 2023c; see also Nie and Zhao, 2017). However, in other inflammatory chronic diseases afflicting the elderly, meta-analyses concluded that the total intake of coffee is not significantly associated with the incidence of either rheumatoid arthritis or osteoarthritis (Lee et al., 2014; Pu et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2023). In parallel, there is some dispute on the contribution of the putative control of inflammation by coffee intake for the onset and/or evolution of age-associated chronic diseases. Thus, some studies provided

compelling evidence that the control of inflammation mediated the ability of coffee intake to attenuate the incidence and burden of type 2 diabetes (Lu et al., 2023; Ochoa-Rosales et al., 2023; Osama et al., 2021) or alcohol-induced hepatic damage (Contaldo et al., 2019; Maki et al., 2010). In contrast, other studies concluded that the inverse association of coffee intake with insulin sensitivity (Rebello et al., 2011), sarcopenia (Iwasaka et al., 2021) or physical performance (Jyväkorpi et al., 2021) was independent of inflammation and other studies were inconclusive to define the contribution of inflammatory control for the ability of coffee intake to attenuate cardiovascular diseases (Daneschvar et al., 2021; Surma et al., 2023).

Probably the more robust evidence for an association between coffee intake and inflammation-mediated chronic diseases in the elderly was provided by the study of aged individuals (over 85 years of age) stratified into low and high NLR4 inflammasome gene expression levels, which correspond to individuals without or with multiple age-related chronic diseases and with high or low levels of caffeine and its metabolites, respectively (Furman et al., 2017). Furthermore, *in vitro* caffeine at physiological concentrations (10–50 μ M) estimated to be found in the plasma of coffee drinkers (Lelo et al., 1986), significantly inhibits the secretion of a pro-inflammatory cytokine, interleukin 1 β because of a decrease in NLR4 gene expression in a cell line (THP-1 cells) derived from an acute monocytic leukemia patient (Furman et al., 2017). This is in agreement with several previous studies in different cellular models showing a role of caffeine mediated by adenosine A_{2A} receptors in the control of inflammation (Ohta and Sitkovsky, 2011; Ouyang et al., 2013). The impact of coffee consumption on inflammation likely involves other components apart from caffeine since decaffeinated coffee also displays anti-inflammatory effects (Cornelis and van Dam, 2020; Hang et al., 2019; Lopez-Garcia et al., 2006). Accordingly, different bioactive constituents of coffee such as chlorogenic acids display anti-inflammatory effects (e.g. Nasef et al., 2022; Victoria-Montesinos et al., 2021) and the total polyphenol intake is inversely associated with inflammatory markers in the UK-based Airwave cohort (Dryer-Beers et al., 2024). Moreover, studies in different human cell lines have demonstrated that both caffeine and chlorogenic acids can attenuate the production of inflammatory markers, such as interleukin 6, tumor necrosis factor α , interferon γ , and transforming growth factor β (Grosso et al., 2017a), through different mechanisms, such as inhibition of pro-inflammatory cytokine gene expression or by the modulation of signal transducer and activator of transcription 1 (STAT1) or nuclear factor kappa-light-chain-enhancer of activated B cells (NF- κ B) pathways (Iris et al., 2018; Nguyen et al., 2024; Ouyang et al., 2013). Thus, there is a rather robust mechanistic rationale to support the ability of coffee intake to control low grade chronic inflammation in the elderly, but efforts are required to ascertain if this coffee-induced control of inflammation is mechanistically responsible for the age-related beneficial effects of coffee.

5.6. Coffee consumption, resilience and adaptation to stress

The aging process is globally characterized by two parallel features: an increased variability of physiological parameters resulting from multiple possible biochemical and physiological solutions adopted by different aged organisms to find similar homeostatic points and an allostatic compression (Timiras, 2007). This implies that any strategy bolstering allostasis, *i.e.* affording a wider interval of possible homeostatic points to adapt to environmental modifications, is expected to preserve healthspan upon aging (Derisbourg et al., 2021). Moreover, if an environmental alteration imbalances an organism into a disease state, it will be perceived as a stressful event; this is signaled intracellularly by biochemical adaptations of primary metabolism eventually triggering oxidative stress in the short term and epigenetic alternations in the longer-term, together with an increased autocrine and paracrine signaling of stress through increased production of inflammatory mediators (Franceschi and Campisi, 2014; Tchkonina et al., 2013) and other

stress signals such as adenosine (Cunha, 2016). Notably, the regular consumption of coffee is particularly effective in controlling allostasis rather than affecting homeostasis, meaning that the regular consumption of coffee is far more effective in providing organisms with the ability to better cope with stressful events rather than affecting non-stressed organisms. Accordingly, the bulk of the evidence previously discussed on the effects of coffee intake on age-associated healthspan and age-associated diseases fits into this contention: coffee intake displays more evident effects to prevent age-associated diseases (counteracting the age-associated allostatic compression) rather than to modify biochemical and physiological parameters of healthy aged individuals (altering homeostasis).

Increasing allostasis implies that coffee intake should bolster the multi-dimensional biological programs that are associated with adaptation to stress. Indeed, the regular intake of coffee is associated with a metabolic re-organization of cells through the heightening of the activity of the major intracellular metabolic maestros, namely AMPK, sirtuins and mTOR (Cetrullo et al., 2015; Yu et al., 2021; Zhao et al., 2020), as previously discussed (Sections 5.3 and 5.4). This has parallel consequences, all coupled to a better adaptation to stress: i) cells become metabolically more efficient, with a focus on adapting primary metabolism to become increasingly dependent on the utilization of fatty acids, the bioenergetically most efficient carbon source with the simplest regulatory profile; ii) cells increase their antioxidant pathways to better cope with adaptive fluctuations of bioenergetic requirements and with a more oxidative (aggressive) environment (hormetic-like adaptive response); iii) cells decrease their production of inflammatory and stress-related signals; iv) cells become less responsive to inflammatory and stress-related signals present in the environment. This combined adaption resulting from coffee intake is mechanistically dependent on the ability of coffee intake to activate key pathways involved in the adaptation to stress such as the pathways operated by the transcription factors nuclear factor- κ B (NF- κ B), nuclear factor erythroid 2-related factor 2 (Nrf2) and aryl hydrocarbon receptor (AhR): the NF- κ B pathway is critically required to mount an inflammatory response through the JAK/STAT proinflammatory signaling pathways (Liu et al., 2017), the Keap1/Nrf2 plays a critical role on cellular protection by regulating many antioxidant and detoxification enzyme genes through the antioxidant response element (ARE) (Ma, 2013) and the AhR-ARNT (aryl hydrocarbon receptor nuclear translocator) recruits xenobiotic response element (XRE) responsive genes to bolster not only detoxification but also chemosensing responses (Serna et al., 2020; Tian et al., 2015). Indeed, several studies have shown that coffee administration is an effective trigger of AhR-mediated gene transcription (Ishikawa et al., 2014; Kalthoff et al., 2010), promoting the recruitment of both detoxification pathways, as reflected by a 30–60 % increased AHR activity, as well as antioxidant pathways, typified by an up-regulation of most Nrf2-pathway genes in intestinal cells (Kalthoff et al., 2010; Toydemir et al., 2021) and also inducing significant increase of nuclear translocation of NF- κ B (up to fivefold) in macrophages, Caco-2 cells, and primary human intestinal microvascular endothelial cells (Sauer et al., 2011) to reduce inflammatory pathways and the responsiveness to inflammation signals (Montenegro et al., 2022). This activation of anti-stress/detoxification pathways has been associated with different constituents of coffee beverages (Boettler et al., 2011), namely chlorogenic acids (Fratantonio et al., 2017; Yao et al., 2019) and caffeine (Hwang et al., 2016; Kanlaya et al., 2021), in accordance with the ability of adenosine A_{2A} receptors to control NF- κ B and Nrf-2 pathways (Mittal et al., 2016; Varani et al., 2011). These different coffee constituents may actually act synergically, as shown by the synergic effects of a formulation of artificial coffee, made up of caffeine and chlorogenic acid, to attenuate LPS-induced inflammatory mediator release and production of radical oxygen species through a combined AMPK phosphorylation, translocation of NF- κ B and of Nrf2 modulating heme oxygenase-1 expression in human keratinocytes (Song et al., 2022).

Apart from these pathways linked to the generation of inflammatory

mediators and detoxification and antioxidant pathways, coffee consumption also triggers a reduced sensitivity of cells to stress related signals, namely inflammatory signals. Thus, chlorogenic acids attenuate the impact of tumor necrosis factor α on cardiomyocytes (Tian et al., 2019), an effect that might involve the regulation of the expression of non-coding regulatory mRNA such as miR-21, miR-30c and miR-96 (Nakayama et al., 2017; Yang et al., 2017). Also, caffeine inhibits NLRP3 inflammasome activation by suppressing MAPK/NF- κ B signaling in 'activated' macrophages (Kovács et al., 2021; Zhao et al., 2019) and caffeine has been reported to develop direct inhibitory effects on STAT1 signaling (Iris et al., 2018), both effects likely involving adenosine A_{2A} receptors that can regulate the trafficking of Toll-like receptor 4 to regulate the sensitivity to inflammation (Haas et al., 2011). Importantly, this caffeine-associated inflammasome sensitivity was reported to allow stratifying older individuals into two extremes in terms of healthspan of their immune-inflammatory system (Furman et al., 2017). However, apart from this relevant report linking age-related healthspan to coffee-induced adaptation to stress, there is still a need for a detailed analysis of the relation between coffee intake and stress-related adaptive pathways in aged adults.

5.7. Coffee consumption and stem cells and regeneration

Although the ultimate goal of medical intervention is the prevention of disease, it is nonetheless evident that treatment strategies will always be required; and the promise of regeneration through the exploitation of stem cells arguably ranks among the most fascinating (Daley, 2012). This is particularly true in the context of aging, where the dream of repairing dysfunctional organs by resorting to stem cells is a promising strategy to achieve rejuvenation (Wang et al., 2019). Conversely, the impact of aging on the ability of stem cells to self-renew and to adequately respond to environmental recruitment signals leads to the physical and functional depletion of the stem cell pools, which is argued to further contribute to the aging process (Brunet et al., 2023). Thus, a considerable effort has been devoted to unveiling mechanisms able to guide and sustain the regenerative potential of stem cells upon aging (Cai et al., 2022). Unfortunately, very little is still known about the potential of coffee constituents to manipulate stem cells and several of these studies have used millimolar concentrations of caffeine, which are never reached in tissues of living animals. The effects of sub-millimolar concentrations of caffeine on different human stem cells *in vitro* have been investigated, showing that caffeine triggers neuronal projection development processes in human neuroepithelial stem cells (Yu et al., 2017) and does not affect the viability of human hippocampal progenitor cells (Houghton et al., 2020). Furthermore, mesenchymal stem cells treated with caffeine increase the phagocytosis of neutrophils (Abbasi et al., 2018) and simultaneously diminish the production of potentially harmful reactive oxygen substances to protect neutrophils from apoptosis (Shushtari et al., 2017). Future work is expected to unravel the role of all four adenosine receptors present in mesenchymal stem cells (Costa et al., 2011; Gharibi et al., 2011), as well as of the Orphan Nuclear Receptor TLX that is responsive to xanthines (Faudone et al., 2021), a goal of prime relevance to foresee a purinergic manipulation of osteogenesis in the context of age-related osteoporosis. This interest is further supported by recent studies linking adenosine receptors to the control of the Wnt/ β -catenin pathway (e.g. Borhani et al., 2019; Yu et al., 2018; Zhang et al., 2017), which plays pleiotropic key roles in regulating embryonic cell development, organogenesis and tissue protection (Liu et al., 2022b). Interestingly, a yeast two-hybrid screening system using human fetal brain cDNA libraries identified a putative target of caffeine - adenosine A_{2A} receptor - as an interactor with the Wnt trafficking protein Wntless (Petko et al., 2018). Additionally, caffeine, but not paraxanthine or theobromine, binds with micromolar affinity to a Wnt deacylase (Zhao et al., 2020b) and chlorogenic acid and coffee extracts modulate the Wnt/ β -catenin pathway in SW-480 cells modelling colorectal cancer cells (Villota et al., 2022). The impact of chlorogenic

acids on human stem cells has also been tested, mainly in the context of a protective potential of chlorogenic acids against the effects of stressful stimuli on stem cells (Andrade et al., 2022; Cherniack et al., 2019; Fang et al., 2024; Khalil Alyahya et al., 2021; Li et al., 2012). Chlorogenic acids were also described to regulate the proliferation and adipogenic differentiation of bone marrow-derived mesenchymal stem cells (Zhou et al., 2015) and the osteogenic differentiation of human dental pulp stem cells (Hu et al., 2021). These preliminary suggestions of parallel effects of caffeine and chlorogenic acids on stem cell viability and differentiation are indicative of an effect of coffee intake on stem cells. However, the existence of scarce and often conflicting information prompts the clear need to clarify the effects of coffee, caffeine and chlorogenic acids on stem cells, which will need to be tested in an *in vivo* setting and in the context of aging. The limited information on the impact of coffee intake on human stem cells is accompanied by a current general ignorance of the regenerative potential of coffee or of coffee constituents in the context of aging. Thus, the regenerative potential of caffeine has been explored in wound healing (Ojeh et al., 2016), in skincare (Elias et al., 2023), in radiation dermatitis in breast cancer patients (Hardy Abeloos et al., 2023), in endothelial repair (Rosenberg et al., 1988; Spyridopoulos et al., 2008), in arthritis (Moases Ghaffary and Abtahi Froushani, 2020), in bone healing (Lopez et al., 2019), in cirrhotic liver regeneration (Dranoff, 2024) but all these studies were conducted in adults. Importantly, there is also robust evidence showing that adenosine might also have a regenerative potential (e.g. IJerman et al., 2022; Lopez et al., 2019), which is not evident to reconcile with a similar effect of caffeine (adenosine activates whereas caffeine blocks adenosine receptors). Future studies should explore if this proposed regenerative potential of caffeine may be extended to elderly individuals and to the consumption of coffee.

6. Concluding remarks

The overall evidence gathered in epidemiological studies is globally suggestive of an impact of the regular consumption of coffee on human aging with the main effect of increasing healthspan on aging and decreasing the incidence of the main age-associated diseases contributing to mortality (Fig. 1). Thus, the regular coffee consumption seems associated with a preservation of muscular, cardiovascular, mental and immune system functions and seems inversely associated with the incidence of the most frequent diseases affecting the elderly such as cardiovascular and respiratory diseases, stroke, some cancers, diabetes, dementia, major depression or frailty. However, it should be emphasized that this beneficial effect has a rather small amplitude and there are discrepancies in some results regarding studies on coffee consumption in humans, which probably results from several factors, namely: i) the current inability to define and segregate the individuals who have larger benefits from those who are less sensitive to coffee, both in terms of metabolism of coffee constituents (pharmacokinetic variability) and on their physiology and targets of coffee constituents (pharmacodynamic variability); ii) the fact that the assessment of regular coffee consumption is mostly done through questionnaires that are potentially biased (not exact) and most often fail to distinguish the different types of coffee endowed with different relative amounts of the different constituents affecting human health; iii) the present efforts to isolate the effects of coffee consumption often do not fully take into account different lifestyle factors that interfere with the impact of coffee intake on human health. The golden standard of controlled intervention studies is difficult to apply to the study of coffee consumption since coffee is widely consumed and freely available and different coffee constituents are present in several foodstuffs also freely available. In spite of these difficulties, future epidemiological studies are certainly warrened to clarify and consolidate several facets of this relation between coffee intake and healthspan on aging such as the personal traits defining coffee benefits and eventually detrimental effects, the definition of optimal doses and schedules of intake of coffee, the clarification of putative side effects, the

particular population of aged individuals who should avoid coffee intake (e.g. some psychiatric patients) and the interference with food matrixes and medications (see Nehlig, 2018). Moreover, further studies on the age-related impact of other foodstuffs, such as tea and chocolate that are also rich in xanthines and polyphenols, may contribute to shed light on the bioactive substances present in coffee that are mainly involved in bolstering healthspan on aging.

Despite these potential pitfalls and open questions, the relation between the regular consumption of coffee and a healthier aging profile gains considerable support with the accumulating evidence that coffee and coffee components can interfere with the identified pillars of aging that format age-associated healthspan and lifespan (Fig. 2). Thus, coffee consumption seems to be associated with decreased genomic instability, epigenetic stability, modulation of metabolic function, control of altered proteostasis and inflammatory processes. Moreover, coffee intake seems to bolster adaptation to stress, allowing to understand how this dietary habit may counteract allostatic compression on aging, thus increasing healthspan in aged individuals. Importantly, the available evidence is still limited, and the conclusions are mostly derived from extrapolations to aged individuals of findings obtained in middle-aged adults: thus, it becomes a priority to carry out research efforts to link coffee intake with these seven pillars of aging, namely inflammation and genomic instability, as well as to understand how coffee and its compounds actually modulate physiological and biochemical processes in aged individuals.

Importantly, this observed convergence of epidemiological findings with mechanistic insights on the benefits of regular coffee consumption to healthspan on aging should prompt two parallel opportunities. From the societal point of view, this pleasurable lifestyle factor should be enjoyed as a 'treasure trove of benefits tailored for the golden years'. From the scientific point of view, the identification of the coffee constituents most effective to counteract the aging process may fuel the development of novel complementary formulations of senostatics (Zhang et al., 2023) and the identification of their molecular targets may be a unique window of opportunity to foster a better understanding of the relative contribution of the different pillars of aging for the biology of aging.

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Declaration of Competing Interest

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